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Enhancing Real-Time 3D Object Reconstruction Using iPhone LiDAR and Photogrammetry Techniques for Virtual Scenes in Unreal Engine

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Declaration

I solemnly declare that the thesis entitled “Enhancing Real-Time 3D Object Reconstruction Using iPhone LiDAR and Photogrammetry Techniques for Virtual Scenes in Unreal Engine” is the result of my own original research work and effort. Unless clearly stated or properly referenced all the subjects and contents in this thesis is based on my own independent research and has not been submitted, either wholly or partially for the fulfilment of any other academic degree or qualification at any university or institution.

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Examining Committee Certification

We certify that we have read this dissertation/thesis: Enhancing Real-Time 3D Object Reconstruction Using iPhone LiDAR and Photogrammetry Techniques for Virtual Scenes in Unreal Engine. and as a committee have examined the student: Zhir Barzan Rafiq in its content and what is related to it. We approve that it meets the standards of a dissertation/thesis for the degree of MSc in Software Engineering

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Dedication

To my mom and dad for their unwavering love, sacrifice, and constant encouragement, which are the basis of all of my achievements.

To my Supervisor, Assist. Prof. Dr. Govand Salih Kadir, for his guidance and belief in my potential.

And Finally to every little kid who was fascinated by computers the first time they used it, and imagined the endless possibilities we can achieve with it. To anyone who was curious like me – this work is for you.

Zhir Barzan Rafiq

Year 2025

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Abstract

It has been said that a picture speaks a thousand words, but it could also have a thousand measurements. This research presents “Project Medusa” a hybrid Scanning mobile application that simplifies and enhances the real time 3D object reconstruction by combining photogrammetry and LIDAR scanning techniques, results of which can later be used in virtual environments such as Unreal Engine. The project name is inspired by the Greek myth of medusa whose gaze could turn every living creature into a stone object, paralleling how modern technology can digitally reconstruct real-world objects with accuracy and precision. Traditional methods of creating 3D models are often time-consuming, resource intensive and costly for purposes like game development and animation. To combat this Project Medusa was developed as a Cost-effective, accurate, and user-friendly mobile solution. The application uses agile methodology for its iterative development and testing, ensuring it is robust, performant and user friendly. Leverages apples native frameworks such as ARKit, and Reality Kit to Process the data entirely on-device, eliminating the need for external computing platforms. Testing and validation consisted of scanning various object under controlled conditions and comparing the results with other existing solutions Like Reality Scan, Polycam, and 3D Scanner App. Project Medusa consistently exhibited the best performance and quality compared to other applications. The application also produced models with efficient mesh geometry, as indicated by its near-ideal vertex-to-face and face-to-vertex ratios, demonstrating a balance between quality and computational efficiency. The final models, exported in USDZ format can be easily integrated and used in a professional virtual environments like 3D Software, Video editing, animation software, Presentation software and game engines, including Unreal Engine.

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List of Abbreviations

3D	Three Dimension
CPU	Central Processing Unit
FBX	Film Box
FSM	Finite State Machine
GCD	Grand Central Dispatch
GPU	Graphical Processing Unit
ICP	Iterative Closest Point
IDE	Integrated Development Environment
IOS	iPhone Operating System
LASER	Light Amplification by Simulated Emission of Radiation
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
MVC	Model-View-Controller
MVVM	Model-View-ViewModel
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
OBJ	Object
OS	Operating System
PC	Personal Computer
RAM	Random Access Memory
SFM	Structure From Motion
UI	User Interface

USDZ Universal Scene Description

UX User Experience

Chapter 1 Introduction

In Greek mythology, there is the terrifying tale of Medusa, a creature in a form of a woman with hair in form of snakes. Possessed with a gaze that could turn any living being into stone object. This ancient story, while fictional finds a compelling modern parallel in the world of three-dimensional (3D) object reconstruction technologies. Modern technologies enable us to reconstruct real-world objects in digital formats with accuracy and precision, transforming fictional stories into reality.

Human imagination has an endless supply of possibilities, stories and environments that we see in movies, games and illustrations that are made by humans. And with modern technology we can turn those imaginations into reality, and we can mainly see the results of these human imaginations in Video games. Video games have become an essential part of our life in a way that we can connect with our friends and family and loved ones, furthermore the market of video games are one of the most rapidly growing markets in the world, according to (Statista, 2025) the video game market revenue is projected to reach \$522.46 billion dollars from all sectors such as mobile, PC and console gaming with mobile having the major share and PC and console following respectively.

The creative process of designing and making games can be a fun and interesting endeavour. One can bring their ideas to life by designing the levels, environments, characters and mechanics inside their game and package it in a way that tells a story many can enjoy playing. However, game development is not an easy process, especially for independent game developers who do not have a lot of resources and manpower to bring their ideas into life, due to the time-consuming nature of game design.

Independent developers must think about every design aspect of their game, from modelling objects and characters, story script, animation, environment design, mechanics, gameplay programming and sound engineering of their game. All these processes on their own take years to master and need extra level of attention and detail depending on the project scale.

Game developers and computer scientist around the world are working hard to

simplify the process of game development. Especially for new developers who are trying to pursue a career in game development industry, it can be very overwhelming to master all those skills as a beginner. One of the most notable companies that has contributed immensely to make this possible is EPIC Game Studio, the creators of Unreal Engine. Unreal Engine is recognized as one of the most robust and powerful game engines in the world, that is used by large game studios and independent developers alike, to create visually breathtaking environments, near real-life animations and fast, optimized games that can run on every platform.

With all these advanced game engines and software's available for game developers to bring their ideas into life, game development is still a time-consuming process, and for someone who is starting to learn game development it can be very overwhelming to learn all of these concepts. However recent advancements in technology have made way to make this process easier, and this can be achieved through the concept of photogrammetry.

Photogrammetry is a way to create 3D Models from 2D images that are taken from various angles. The way it works is that the photogrammetry program takes all the pictures and finds the main common points between them and detects the shape and size of that specific object and reconstructs that said shape in a 3D format based on their spatial placement that were obtained from the 2D images.

This helps game developers bring real life objects into their games and bring their ideas into life. Even though it's a great way to make 3D objects it is not very accurate, the reason behind this is that there are several factors that contribute noise to the final product or the image that is being used to create the 3D model such as, light conditions, camera quality, surface texture and reflectivity, camera movement and blur, background complexities and angles of the shot that is taken. These factors might contribute to some noise or unwanted disturbances in your 3D model making it inaccurate and useless.

There has been many advancements to make Photogrammetry more accurate and precise when it comes to the final result but one of the best ways that has had very outstanding results is the use of laser sensors to create photogrammetry

models, where we can measure the distance from the device to the surface of the object in a more accurate way and create the 3D models based on the data that we get from those measurements.

However, these tools are not cheap, in fact they can be extremely expensive depending on their specification, but there is a way where we can use those technologies for free by using our smartphones. Most of the smartphones nowadays come with many extraordinary technologies that we can use to our advantage they include many sensors that are able to capture those types of data very easily.

One of those sensors that can contribute heavily to our research is the LIDAR sensors that are available on iPhone pro models. LIDAR which stands for (Light Detection and Ranging) Is an extremely specific device that measures the distance between 2 objects in the real world by emitting laser lights. The way it works is that it sends laser lights or pulses to the surface of the object and those pulses deflect from the object and comes back to the sensor, by measuring the time it takes for the pulse to return to the sensor we can calculate the exact location of the surface which the pulse hits, they are used in many real life products especially the self-driving cars in fact is due to this technology that is possible to have self-driving cars.

Figure 1.1 Photogrammetry VS LIDAR

The use of this sensor can help us immensely in achieving accurate 3D models that are ready for use immediately after they are captured. In this research we will explore how we can achieve this result and contribute the knowledge that we

gain for the field of photogrammetry.

1.1 Problem Statement

Traditional methods for creating 3D objects or models for multimedia purposes such as game development and animation is often time consuming, resource-intensive, and costly, with potential inaccuracies in the result. While modern photogrammetry and LIDAR-based tools and equipment's offer automated alternatives. These tools can be very expensive depending on their specifications and complex to operate. Although advancements in smartphone hardware, particularly in the integration of LIDAR sensors pave the way for new opportunities, real-time 3D reconstruction on mobile devices remains limited by hardware constraints, environmental factors, and software challenges. This research work addresses the need for a cost-effective, accurate, and user-friendly mobile solution capable of generating detailed 3D models in real time, by overcoming these technical limitations.

1.2 Objective

The main goal of this research is to investigate the accuracy and precision of 3D reconstruction of a real-life object so that it could be used in game creation and development, Using LIDAR sensors and photogrammetry techniques. To accomplish this result we will focus on:

1. Develop a hybrid scanning mobile application that allows 3D object reconstruction on mobile devices, results of which can later be used in virtual environments.
2. Reduce the processing time it takes to reconstruct 3D objects on mobile devices.

1.3 Contributions

This research work contributes to the field of 3D object reconstruction through the development of Project Medusa, a Novel iOS application that combines photogrammetry and LIDAR Scanning to achieve real-time 3D model generation

entirely on device. This application uses apples native technologies and frameworks such as Apple's AR kit, Reality Kit and Object Capture Frameworks, that leverages the structure from motion algorithm to create a 3D point cloud, in addition to the data acquired from the LIDAR sensor along with the use of iterative closest point algorithm, to align the data and achieve better geometrical accuracy and realism. Furthermore, the generated results of this Mobile application can later be used in professional virtual environments for multimedia creation purposes.

1.4 Thesis Organization

This thesis contains of six chapters:

- Chapter 1: introduces the concepts of photogrammetry and LIDAR, explains the context of the thesis, defines the problem statement, outlines the objectives, highlights the contributions made in the field, defines the scope of the study.
- Chapter 2: presents a detailed literature review covering photogrammetry and LIDAR scanning techniques, and their integration with other software tools and their use-cased in real-world applications.
- Chapter 3: defines the methodology that is used in order to design, develop and evaluate the mobile application including research design, tools and technologies, system architecture, data collection and validation strategies,
- Chapter 4: explains the implementation details of the mobile application, from initial design to the application development prototype and its integration with virtual environments like unreal engine.
- Chapter 5: discuss the result of the application and reflects on the mobile application overall performance and usability.
- Chapter 6: concludes the research work with suggestion for future research development and improvement.

Chapter 2 Literature Review

This chapter of the research investigates works that have been conducted in the field of photogrammetry and the use of LIDAR technologies in 3D object reconstruction. This investigation aims to find a way to combine the two techniques to enhance the results of photogrammetry and its main objective is to find a way to make this happen on mobile devices. It also examines their integration with virtual environments such as Unreal Engine and Blender, and how 3D objects that have been scanned can be reused in projects and game development environments and mainstream video games.

Furthermore, this chapter examines both the hardware and software capabilities of current devices and the advancements that have been made in the field of mobile hardware technologies, as the main goal is to create an application that handles the task of 3D object reconstruction completely on a mobile device rather than the use of a personal PC.

This research also investigates the modern software architectures and the different architectures of mobile operating systems and the process of App development for mobile devices, and how their respective architectures can aid in achieving the main objective. It also addresses the potential challenges and obstacles, particularly the limitations of photogrammetry, more specifically in environments with poor lighting as well as the surfaces with reflective textures or objects with complex geometrical shapes.

2.1 Background information on photogrammetry

The Science of photogrammetry originates to the mid-19th century, when scholars and engineers first began using photographic images to extract spatial information from the physical world. One of the earliest examples of photogrammetry is the work of Aimé Laussedat, also known as “Father of photogrammetry”, (Shown in Figure 2.1) in 1858 used photographs to create topographical maps of planes. The process consisted of taking images from different positions and using the principle of perspective to measure and map objects. His work introduces the foundational principles that 2D photographs could be

transformed into a 3D spatial data using mathematical projection models (Schenk, 2005).

Figure 2.2 Aimé Laussedat, Father of photogrammetry

Figure 2.1 Topographic Map

As photography advanced through the late 19th century and early 20th century, photogrammetry became an essential concept in the field, allowing for creation of highly detailed topographic maps. Over the century, the field evolved significantly, mainly with the dawn of airborne photography during World War 1 which made large-scale mapping a reality. Using mathematical equations and

models to correct the distortions in the calculations of the angles and points on the image further enhancing the accuracy the digital revolution in the late-20th century completely transformed photogrammetry, by digitalizing the whole process, allowing for faster and more precise 3D model generation. Figure 2.2 shows an example of Topographic Map.

With the digital revolution photogrammetry transitioned from analog photographic measurements to digital image processing the automation of image matching edge detection, and feature recognition techniques allowed researchers to reconstruct more accurate 3D structures using Structure From Motion or (SFM) algorithms, which estimates camera movement and reconstructs a 3D structure from overlapping 2D images, and represent the cumulation of these developments.

While photogrammetry relies on optical imagery to reconstruct 3D models, LIDAR scanning, on the other hand is a more recent technology. It goes back to 1960s with the invention of laser (light amplification by simulated emission of radiation). Early LIDAR systems were developed mainly for military and aerospace purposes, mainly used for satellites tracking. In the 1970s, NASA used LIDAR technology for lunar mapping during the Apollo 15 mission.

LIDAR technology became more widely available for during 1980s and 1990s mainly used for airborne topographic mapping. LIDAR technologies became mainstream in the early 21st century and the development of it expanded and its applications to fields like archaeology and urban planning. The most recent and significant development of LIDAR technology is its integration in consumer devices such as smartphone devices. Which has made the technology accessible for everyday use and real-time 3D scanning.

2.2 Literature Review

Early research by (Schenk, 2005) established the mathematical and algorithmic principles of photogrammetry, emphasizing the transformation of 2D images into 3D models through triangulation and camera calibration. The author detailed how overlapping images can reconstruct spatial geometry by determining camera

orientation, internal parameters, and focal distances. This theoretical framework remains central to modern digital photogrammetry.

Additionally In the world of 3D object reconstruction, the concepts of both photogrammetry and LIDAR scanning have gained significant attention as balancing techniques that considerably enhance the reliability of digital models. the concept of photogrammetry manipulates overlapping images taken from various angles to recreate a comprehensive 3D model and its textures. Meanwhile, the concept of LIDAR scanning precisely captures the complexity data of the 3D model, thereby refining the accuracy and extensiveness of the object recreation (Kim et al., 2022)

The combination of both photogrammetry and Lidar scanning techniques can overcome obstacles such as reflective surfaces, low-light conditions, and complicated geometrical shapes where one of the techniques may fail to capture all the essential details (Chang et al., 2023).

In modern research, the focus has shifted toward mobile LIDAR scanning and the sensors capable of achieving this, specifically those sensors present in modern smartphone devices, in order to enable real-time 3D object reconstruction. (Sheshtar et al., 2025) demonstrated that the LIDAR sensor available in Apple's iPhone devices are capable of achieving almost perfect levels of accuracy in controlled situations, which opens up endless possibilities for quickly scanning diverse real-world objects.

Similarly (Zhang et al. 2022) investigated the fusion of photogrammetry and LIDAR scanning data for urban arrangement planning. This resulted in a more comprehensive 3D model compared to the data obtained from each method alone.

In the world of game development, Unreal Engine plays an essential role in the visualization and handling of these 3D reconstructed models. (Cheng, Y., Li, F., & Zhao, Q. (2021)) examined the technique of importing LIDAR-generated point clouds into a virtual environment like Unreal Engine, observing that the engine's advanced rendering features can handle high-fidelity conception of complicated scenes. This makes Unreal Engine one of the best game development software for creating high-end games, architectural scenes and simulated prototyping. Figure 2.3 shows the scanning process of photogrammetry vs LIDAR.

Figure 2.3 Scanning Process of Photogrammetry vs LIDAR

Nevertheless, combining the concepts of photogrammetry and LIDAR scanning data is a significant task often demanding very sophisticated algorithms and techniques to manage the noise generated during scanning, the reduction of those noises, data merging from the two techniques and resolution inconsistencies (Alwan et al., 2022).

Even with the technical obstacles of these two techniques, most recent studies highlight enhancements in hardware technologies, such as more capable sensor technologies and faster, more efficient mobile processors, as well as more modern software technologies, such as enhanced photogrammetry algorithms and machine learning. These advancements can improve and optimize the performance of 3D object reconstruction techniques and methods (Kim et al.,

2022;) and (Chang et al., 2023). Equally, these technological advancements lay the foundation for easier-to-use and effective modern solutions for incorporating photogrammetry and LIDAR scanning into workflows and virtual environments by capturing and reconstructing 3D objects in real-time and processing and rendering those specific models on devices. This reduces the time it takes to create a 3D model compared to traditional 3D modelling from scratch. Building upon the foundational understanding of both photogrammetry and LIDAR techniques, this section delves into their individual performances, comparing them primarily in terms of accuracy and efficiency during the reconstruction of the 3D object. This Analysis is essential for identifying the best possible solution between the two and for integrating them into virtual environments.

In the latest findings, scientists have assessed the precision of mobile LIDAR sensors, especially those available on Apple's iPhone devices, and compared them with more traditional tools and photogrammetry techniques. (Sheshtar, Alhatlani, Moulden, & Kim, 2025) conducted an experiment using LIDAR sensor and photogrammetry solutions available on iPhone 15 Pro max to test the devices' capabilities in an organized environment mimicking a real crime scene. The results showed that the LIDAR sensor is more accurate with the accuracy of 0.012 meters, while the photogrammetry techniques showed a marginally smaller accuracy of 0.017 meters. The results of this experiment indicate that both methods are practical solutions for reconstructing a high-detail 3D model, with LIDAR scanning providing slightly higher accuracy in some specific scenarios

One of the most critical factors in choosing a 3D reconstruction technique is the level of efficiency in data acquisition and the processing time for that said data. When using photogrammetry, it is often necessary to capture multiple clear images from various angles, and the number of images sometimes requires a lot of post processing. This enables quicker scans of the 3D objects in a fraction of the time it takes for traditional 3D modelling (Jason Laan, 2021).

2.3 Summery

In summery this literature explores the evolution of 3D model scanning and examine their accuracy and efficiency through the years. Recent studies show

that both Photogrammetry and LIDAR Scanning are effective for 3D object reconstruction, with LIDAR often having a slight Edge in terms of accuracy compared to photogrammetry. The ideal use-case for both concepts depend on the project's specific requirements. Photogrammetry excels at capturing the textures on the surface of the object in a luminous environment, while LIDAR is better for complex shapes and low-Light scanning or reflective objects. The combination of these two methods is presented as solution for their respective limitations.

Chapter 3 Methodology

This chapter outlines the methods that are used in designing, developing and testing our hybrid scanning mobile application prototype, code named (Project Medusa) taking inspiration from the Greek mythology Story mentioned in Chapter 1. This chapter is organised as follows: Section 3.1 discusses the research design. Section 3.2 explains the system architecture of the mobile application. Section 3.3 outlines the tools and Technologies that are used in implanting this prototype. Section 3.4 explains the data collection methods. Section 3.5 explains the testing and validation approach.

3.1 Research Design

This research work follows an experimental design methodology aimed at designing, developing and evaluating a hybrid scanning mobile application in order to enable 3D object reconstruction on mobile devices. The goal is to create an easy to use, light weight and scalable solution that can be used in any environment and scenes, the results of which can later be used by third party applications for multimedia purposes.

This proposed prototype is evaluated against other well-known existing solutions in the market in terms of reconstruction quality, processing time, generated file size, usability and performance, using standardized testing conditions, across all of the solutions.

3.1.1. Agile methodology

To manage the constant iterative development and testing of Project Medusa mobile application, this research work adopted the agile software development methodology. Agile was chosen due to its adaptability, flexibility and its emphasis on incremental progress and continuous feedback, which aligns with the experimental prototype-driven nature of the mobile application.

The implementation process was divided into short manageable sprints. Each focused on implementing a specific module of the application and thorough testing of that specific module. After each sprint the outcomes of the

implementation were evaluated, and adjustments were made based on the results of the test and the performance metrics. This approach facilitated rapid development of the prototype, and allowed for detection of issues, and enabled ongoing refinement of the system architecture and constant updates to the user interface of the mobile application, ensuring the prototype is robust, performant and user-friendly.

The development lifecycle was divided into 4 focused sprints, (shown in Figure 3.1 and 3.2) each focusing on implementing a core component of the system architecture. This structure enabled simultaneous refinement and performance evaluation and enhancement. After each sprint, comprehensive testing and code refactoring and subsequent planning were done ensuring continuous improvement and optimization. The sprint structure was as follows:

- Sprint 1: UI/UX design and system architecture design
- Sprint 2: Photogrammetry module
- Sprint 3: Real-time Processing and mesh generation
- Sprint 4: LIDAR integration

Agile Lifecycle of Project Medusa

Figure 3.1 Agile Lifecycle of Project Medusa

Sprint life cycle of Project Medusa

Figure 3.2 Sprint Lifecycle of Project Medusa

3.2 System Architecture

Project Medusa mobile application prototype developed for this research follows an organized and structured architecture in order to support real-time 3D reconstruction. For this purpose, the model-view-ViewModel or MVVM mobile architecture was adopted to improve the overall system architecture of the application, furthermore the finite state machine or FSM computational model was implemented in the mobile application to manage the different states of the application.

3.2.1. Model-View-ViewModel Architecture

One of the most widely used software architectures in the software development industry, that is adopted by many tech giants such as Airbnb and Netflix. Its also the one of the architectural patterns that is recommend by Apple to be used by developers to create desktop and mobile applications for Apple products alongside MVC (Model-View-Controller).

MVVM architecture offers a structured, organized and easy to understand approach of designing software. By separating the Data layer from the main

business logic layer and the user interface (UI) layer of the mobile application, allowing the application to achieve modularity and easy maintainability, by separating those modules into their own individual modules which makes it easier to design, develop and test those said modules separately and detect issues the application faster and more effectively. Figure 3.3 below illustrates the core structure of MVVM architecture:

Figure 3.3 Core Structure of MVVM architecture

3.2.2. Finite State Machine

A finite state machine (FSM) is a computational model used to design systems that transition between a finite number of states based on the user interaction or main logic of the system. FSM is widely adopted when it comes to state management of mobile applications, especially for applications that have very complex workflows with well-defined transitions.

Project Medusa adopts FSM to control the application behaviour and the transition between the different states of the application during the 3D scanning process. Each scanning session transitions through individual pre-defined states

such as Initialization, Detection, Capture, Processing, and Completion. These distinct states represent the logical phases of the scan and ensure that the application acts predictably to user interactions.

The FSM approach enhances the reliability and user experience by guiding the users through the scanning process, minimizing scanning errors, and preventing the invalid operations in the application. By enforcing a structured flow, it ensures consistency in data capture and 3D model generation across different scanning sessions. Figure 3.4 below present a simplified diagram of the FSM model used in the application:

Figure 3.4 Simplified diagram of the FSM Model in Project Medusa

3.2.3. Data Flow

The flow of data within Project Medusa outlines the sequence of operations that transform raw sensor data that is obtained during the capture process, into a complete reconstructed 3D model. The flow of the application takes a structured linear approach through the scanning process while still maintain the real-time performance, minimizing latency, and ensuring consistent reconstruction quality without losing any visual fidelity.

Upon launching Project Medusa, the user has the choice to choose between object or environment scanning, after which the initialization phase starts, where the necessary hardware components are activated and the environment is calibrated. In the detection phase real-time feedback is provided to guide user alignment along the capture orbit. Once the scanning starts, the application transitions into the capture phase during which images are taken from the camera sensor along with LIDAR depth data by the LIDAR sensor based on the respective position of the user.

When the capture process is finished, the application transitions into the

processing phase, in which the captured data from both of the sensors will be aggregated into a structured 3D mesh with its original textures. This includes the photogrammetric stitching of overlapping images, and integration of LIDAR depth data to enhance the overall geometric accuracy of the scanned object. Once completed, the completion phase allows the user to preview, interact with, share or export the resulting generated 3D model in. USDZ format.

This defined data flow of Project Medusa ensures a simple, modular, efficient and effective 3D model reconstruction that focuses on user-guided experience. Figure 3.5 below illustrates the complete data flow of Project Medusa:

Figure 3.5 Data Flow Diagram of Project Medusa

3.3 Tools and Technologies

The development process of Project Medusa application prototype required very specific hardware and software devices and technologies. Due to some devices lacking the necessary sensors that was required to achieve the desired results, and have the processing power to handle real-time capture of those data types and processing.

This necessitated the use of technologies or smartphone that have all of the required components that will help in achieving the desired result. For this purpose, Apple iPhone devices were selected as the main testing device for testing and deployment of the application. Apple's iPhone devices especially iPhone pro Line of products are equipped with a built in LIDAR sensor and a high-performance camera module, along with great processing power and battery life. That would boost the development and the testing phases in the development life cycle of Project Medusa.

The required and recommend technology to develop IOS applications for Apple devices is swift programming language. And in order to create applications for IOS devices, it is required to use a computer with MacOS operating system which is required to run Xcode integrated development environment (IDE) which is the required IDE to develop applications for IOS devices.

Additional development and testing were conducted using a MacBook Air with a M4 and a high-performance custom Windows PC for processing the models in 3D environments such as Unreal Engine and MeshLab. Below is the list of all the hardware and software Tools and technologies that were used in the design, development and testing of Project Medusa mobile application:

3.3.1. Hardware Setup:

- Apple iPhone 15 Pro: this device was used as the primary testing and development platform. It included a built-in LIDAR sensor, a high-resolution 48Mpx Camera array, and an A17 pro Chip which is a very powerful Chip that was developed in-house by Apple and its capable of handling real-time 3D

processing and rendering tasks effectively.

- Apple MacBook Air (M4): used as the main development machine. It provides all the tools and technologies that was developed by Apple and it allows us to develop applications natively for Apple devices such as MacOS and IOS using Apples own in-house tools and technologies such as Xcode and IOS simulator that was beneficial for our development, testing and deployment stages of the implementation phase.
- Testing objects: various test objects with different characteristics and surfaces were used as part of the test, in order to see the results of application in action and these objects were chosen specifically so that it covers most of the areas of our test some with surface textures that are smooth and some of them are very complex or have reflective surfaces Textures.
- Custom PC: a custom PC that was mainly used to run Unreal Game Engine and Reality Scan Programs since they are desktop applications and they work better with a dedicated GPU.

3.3.2. Software Setup:

- Swift Programming Language: in order to create a native IOS application one is required to use Swift programming language as their main language, Swift is a very robust, modern and High-performance programming language that is developed by Apple, and its main purpose is to create high-quality and performant native applications for Apple devices. It also features safety, and it has native compatibility with IOS frameworks.
- Xcode IDE: Apple main integrated Development Environment (IDE) which is required, in order to create an IOS application. And without the use of Xcode one cannot test their application on their device, Xcode was chosen for suitability with Apple's native technologies and it's amazing features that one can use to track the process that are happening in the application during testing.
- Swift UI: it's a user interface framework that is developed and recommended

by Apple for developers to create visually stunning User interfaces using its declarative structure and real-time previews that allow for a rapid UI/UX development.

- AR Kit: it's an Apple framework that allows access to the LIDAR sensor, spatial tracking and point cloud data which are essential to use in Project Medusa application since the whole design is centered around the use of the camera and the LIDAR sensor.
- Reality Kit: it's an Apple framework that is mainly used for processing and rendering the models and displaying the 3D objects in and augmented reality. Which is great for viewing and examine the models that were captured to preview them before and post processing.
- Scene Kit: it's an Apple framework that is mainly used to manipulate and 3D meshes and display them in custom virtual environment based on the applications requirement. It also allows Project Medusa application to share and export the scan models universally through different 3rd party applications such as email services and instant messaging applications in .USDZ file format
- Git: a version control system that was used to keep track of the changes that were done to Project Medusa application, in order to keep track of all the changes that were happening in our application. And return to the previous versions, in case a new version did not work as intended for this purpose we used git which is a very well-known and robust version control system that is used by many developers to keep track of the changes that they do to their software.
- Unreal Engine: a robust, feature rich game engine developed by Epic Games Studio, used by many game studios and independent developers to develop games, movies, and animations with very high-quality 3D graphics. Unreal Engine was utilized to perform visual evaluation of the 3D reconstructed models by Project Medusa and demonstrate their use cases in a virtual environment such as Unreal Engine.

- MeshLab: an open-source 3D data processing software that is capable of processing, cleaning, rendering and editing 3D meshes, MeshLab was utilized for data collection of the individual meshes that were generated by Project Medusa.

3.4 Data Collection

in this section we will explain the ways that Project Medusa acquired, checked and stored the data that was collected from both the LIDAR sensor and camera sensor, also how the environment was setup to capture the data and how the data that was captured are tested, evaluated and validated to see the performance, quality and comparative analysis of Project Medusa. Figure 3.6 shows the sequence Diagram of Project Medusa.

Figure 3.6 sequence Diagram of Project Medusa

3.4.1. Environment Setup

To achieve the best possible result for the collection of data and later stages of processing, the data was captured in a controlled lighting conditions to minimize unwanted noise, glare, and reflection issues during the scanning process. This controlled luminous environment ensured that the captured data from the scanning process were high-quality and suitable for comparison and visual

evaluation.

3.4.2. Data Acquisition

The data acquisition of Project Medusa consists of a synchronized collection of high-quality image capture and depth data capture using iPhone built-in camera module by using the camera sensor and LIDAR sensor respectively. This multi sensor scanning approach enables Project Medusa to generate highly detailed, visually accurate 3D models directly on device.

The photogrammetry process uses SFM or structure from motion pipeline which is powered by Apples object capture feature which is a part of Reality Kit framework. SFM reconstructs 3D objects by estimating the camera's motion path by analysing multiple 2D images captured from various angles around the object and generates a light 3D point cloud as a result. SFM relies on the pinhole camera projection equation which is shown below:

$$x = P \cdot X \dots \dots \dots 3.1$$

Where:

- x = 2D image point
- X = 3D point in world coordinates
- $P = K[R|t]$ = camera projection matrix (intrinsic matrix K , rotation R , translation t)

The result of this calculation is a visually rich but geometrically light 3D representation of the reconstructed model. Figures 3.7 and 3.8 below explain the SFM process in action:

Figure 3.8 SFM Scanning Method

Figure 3.7 Result of SFM, light 3D point clouds

While SFM offers a very texture rich data, the LIDAR sensor captures precise geometrical data. Using the time-of-flight method. The iPhone’s LIDAR sensor emits pulses of near-infrared laser light and measures how long they take to return after bouncing off surfaces. As its shown in the equation below:

$$d = \frac{c * t}{2} \dots\dots\dots 3.2$$

Where:

- $d = \text{distance to the surface}$
- $c = \text{speed of light}$
- $t = \text{round trip time of the laser pulse}$

The outcome of this is a dense depth map or point cloud of the scene, which is particularly useful in complex environments or shapes like low-light environments or texture-less surfaces. Figure 3.9 Below explains how LIDAR sensor acquires data .

Figure 3.9 LIDAR (Time of flight) Method

With the aquasition of both the images and the point clouds, comes the process of combineing and merging The visual SFM and geometric LIDAR data into a

single unified 3D model. This process is called data alignment, in which the captured data will be registered and synchronized and ready for processing. The Apple object Capture framework handles this integration internally using iterative closest point or (ICP) alignment.

The ICP refines the conversion between SFM-generated point clouds and LIDAR point clouds by minimizing the distance between matching points across the data sets. The combined dataset preserves the high-resolution textures capture from the photogrammetry and the precise geometrical accuracy from the LIDAR sensor. This fusion process in Project Medusa results in both photorealistic and metrically reliable, with significantly enhanced visual fidelity reconstruction of 3D models. Figure 3.10 below shows the ICP process during initial pose and final result:

Figure 3.10 Iterative closest point (ICP) Method in action

3.4.3. Data Storage and Organization

The captured data from the sensors is automatically stored in a dedicated folder in the local app storage, this folder include the captured images from all angles and also the LIDAR depth maps, this folder will be updated as the user captures more data of the scanned. In the processing stage the data that is stored in the said folder will be processed into a 3D model based on the images and the depth map data from the sensors.

Each session of the scan generates a 3D model from the images and the spatial data that is stored in the dedicated folder, in which the generated model will be stored as a USDZ (universal scene description) file format. .USDZ file format is a lightweight 3D file format initially developed by Pixar company, it was designed mainly for AR and VR experiences, by packaging all the 3D main components such as (material, textures, and geometry) into one single package, thus simplifying sharing, viewing and interaction with the objects in this file format.

3.4.4. Data Quality Check

After each capture session, the generated 3D model is displayed in a virtual environment for the user to review. The user can manipulate, compare, evaluate the visual elements or reshoot the model depending on its quality. This immediate feedback loop ensures a user-friendly experience and facilitates iterative improvements. The exported object can later be used in any software that supports .USDZ file format and can be used for any multimedia purpose that the user desires.

3.5 Testing and Validation

This section of the research work focuses on validating the performance and quality of the proposed real-time 3D scanning prototype that was developed as part of the experimental work of this research work. Project Medusa combines both photogrammetry and LIDAR techniques on Apple's IOS devices, the primary objective of this test is to evaluate the processing speed, output optimization and the visual quality of the reconstructed 3D object in comparison with existing solutions.

For this purpose, a controlled evaluation outline was planned, this outline involved scanning a fixed set of objects using Project Medusa and three other widely known 3D scanning software applications. Each application was tested under identical environmental conditions to ensure a unbiased and reliable comparative analysis.

3.5.1. Performance Evaluation

The performance evaluation focused on processing time and file size, two critical indicators of application efficiency. The outline for evaluating the performance of these applications was carefully designed and executed in the following way:

A set of eight real-world objects, detailed in the appendix, was carefully selected for the scanning process. For each specific object 80 images were captured from various angles of the real-life object, in a luminous environment using each of the selected application. The software applications that were chosen for this evaluation are:

1. Project Medusa: the developed mobile application prototype as part of this research's experimental work. It combines both photogrammetry and LIDAR scanning techniques to enhance the accuracy of the reconstructed models. It's only available on LIDAR-Enabled devices.
2. Reality Scan: formerly known as (Reality Capture) is a photogrammetry software developed by Epic Games that allows for creation of highly detailed 3D model by scanning the models, it's available for Microsoft Windows operating system only.
3. Polycam: is a cross-platform photogrammetry mobile application that is developed by Polycam Inc. which allows for creation of 3D models using photogrammetry and environments using LIDAR scanning. It's available on IOS and Android operating systems.
4. 3D Scanner App: it's IOS, iPad OS and MacOS photogrammetry application that is developed by Laan Labs that allows for LIDAR scanning for environments, editing and measurement of generated 3D models from your device. It's only available on Pro models of iPhone and iPad devices.

The metrics measured for each application were the processing time, defined as the duration to generate the reconstruction of the captured 3D model, and the respective file size of the generated 3D object, to achieve model consistency across all applications, all scans were performed under identical lighting and

environmental conditions, using the same iPhone device camera and LIDAR sensor thus guaranteeing fairness in the comparison.

For each application the processing time and the file size of each object were measured, the collected data were later formulated to facilitate comprehensive comparison of the overall performance of the applications. This method allowed for direct observation of the overall computational efficiency and optimization achieved by Project Medusa compared to the other applications in real-world scenarios.

3.5.2. Quality Evaluation

in addition to performance evaluation, the visual elements and the geometric quality of the reconstructed 3D models were evaluated. This evaluation was conducted using MeshLab Software, which is an open-source software that is primarily used to process 3D data processing. MeshLab software offers a robust set of tools and features such as model editing, cleaning, healing, inspecting, rendering and converting large unstructured 3D triangular meshes.

This step was crucial in verifying the Project Medusa not only exhibits superior performance in terms of processing time and file size optimization but also generates high-quality 3D reconstructed models. The evaluation criteria at this stage encompassed the assessment of the following dimensions:

- **Texture Resolution:** this evaluated the clarity and visual fidelity of the generated 3D model in comparison with the real-life object.
- **Surface Geometry:** this evaluated the smoothness of the object's surfaces by collecting the vertex count of each of the objects and identifying the presence of any detectable noise.
- **Mesh Density:** this referred to the actual polygon counts of the object, serving as a representation of the model's level of detail.
- **Visual Inspection:** this involved a side-by-side comparison of each object within unreal engine environment.

For the actual evaluation process of the generated 3D models, each generated object from their respective applications, was exported into both USDZ and OBJ file formats, accounting for some software's limited support for different file types. After which each object from each application was imported to unreal engine for consistent visualization. A visual comparison of each object was performed of each object was then performed within the real-time environment of the unreal engine. Their quality was assessed based on how effectively they preserved their original look of the real-life object.

3.5.3. Comparative Analysis

In order to determine the effectiveness of Project Medusa application against the other existing solutions, a side-by-side analysis of the performance and the quality of the generated 3D models for each object across all applications will be conducted. This analysis will include the results of processing time, file size, vertex count and polygon count of each 3D object that was scanned during our tests.

A vertex count is the number of vertecies in a 3D model that are essentially the points or corners where the edges of a 3D shape meet, it is used to measure the complexity of a mesh in the context of 3D model, along with the polygon count or faces of the 3D object which is the number of triangles that the 3D model generates. The higher the number of the polygons the more detailed our object would appear, however this means it requires more processing power and storage when it comes to rendering the caputred object.

Furthermore, a compartive analysis will be conducted concerning the relationship between the vertex count (V) and the number of faces or polygon counts (F) in each of the 3D reconstructed models by each application. The ratios of vertex-to-face and face-to-vertex will be formulated, which are curcial indicators in 3D mesh evaluation and analysis, it also provides valuble insights of the sturctural efficiency and complexity of the reconstructed 3D model.

The V/F ratio represents the average number of vertices per face. A low ratio of V/F usually indicates that the faces are more complex, possibly sharing more

vertices, or it could possibly suggest that the mesh contains higher number of non-triangular faces. The equation below describes the relationship of V/F as shown in equation 3.3:

$$V / F \text{ ratio} = \frac{\text{vertex count}}{\text{polygon count}} \dots\dots\dots 3.3$$

In the context of 3D scanning, V/F ratio close to 0.5 for triangular meshes, where each face has exactly 3 vertices and each interior vertex naturally shared by 6 Faces, suggests an efficiently decorated mesh. Deviations in the ratio might possibly indicate issues like isolated vertices or highly stretched triangles in the 3D model. The table below explains the basic interpretations of the V/F ratio:

Table 3.1 V/F Ratio Scale Table

V/F Ratio	Value	Analysis
Normal	≈ 0.5	Perfect triangle mesh.
Low	< 0.4	Unused or excess vertices or non-triangular shape.
High	> 0.6	Too many vertices or over-detailed faces.
Minimum	= 0	Very few Vertices, likely broken geometry or error.
Maximum	= 1	Nearly 1 vertex per face, insufficient mesh.

On the contrary the F/V ratio represents the average number of faces per vertex. A high F/V ratio generally indicates that each vertex is share by a greater number of faces, which generally desirable for efficient mesh representations as it suggests more compact and interconnected structure. The equation below describes the relationship of F/V as shown in equation 3.4:

$$F / V \text{ ratio} = \frac{\text{poygon count}}{\text{vertex count}} \dots\dots\dots 3.4$$

For a triangular mesh an F/V ratio around 2.0 considering the interior vertices are sharing 6 faces and each having 3 vertices, it usually observed as a well-formed mesh. The table below explains the basic interpretations of the F/V ratio:

Table 3.2 F/V ratio Scale Table

F/V Ratio	Value	Analysis
Normal	≈2.0	Perfect triangle mesh.
Low	< 1.9	Low connectivity, looser mesh
High	> 2.1	Over decorated, possibly structurally unstable.
Minimum	= 1.0	No reuse, open or insufficient mesh.
Maximum	= 3.0	Very dense mesh, possible overuse of points.

Both the V/F and F/V ratios are crucial to the results of the research, they provide a quantitative metric for assessing the geometric quality and efficiency of the reconstructed 3D models. A model with an optimal balance in these ratios is suggestive of a good mesh topology, which is essential for later uses of them in rendering, animation, game development and 3D printing use-cases.

Additionally these ratios help in identifying the potential issues in the reconstruction process, such as over-tessellation which is where too many faces are given for a given vertex count, or under-tessellation which is too few faces to properly represent the surface detail of the reconstructed object. Understanding these ratios allows for a more significant evaluation beyond just raw polygon count, indicating how effectively the polygons are being used to represent the 3D geometry of the reconstructed object.

Theoretical Bases of V/F and F/V ratios:

In order to understand the relevance and importance of both V/F and F/V ratios, it is essential to explore their mathematical and geometric foundation. These ratios are derived from Euler's Polyhedron formula, which is the most fundamental equations in geometry and computer graphics for defining the relationship between structural components of any polygon mesh. Euler's formula is defined as follows:

$$V - E + F = x \dots\dots\dots 3.5$$

Where:

- V = represents the number of vertices
- E = represents the number of edges that connect to those vertices
- F = represents the number of faces or polygons that form the surface
- x = Euler's characteristic of the surface. (= 2 for manifold 3D objects)

This equation forms the foundation of 3D mesh Topology, and is widely used in computational geometry, 3D modelling, and computer-generated graphics to describe how the vertices, edges and faces of an object are related to each other. It essentially ensures that the model structure remains consistent and mathematically sound.

In the context of triangular meshes which are the most commonly used types of meshes in 3D graphics and photogrammetry, each face consists of exactly 3 Edges and each edge is typically shared by two faces. From this relationship we can derive that:

$$3F = 2E \dots\dots\dots 3.6$$

By substituting this equation into Euler's formula, we can simplify the expression to find the relationship between the number of the vertices and the number of faces. Substituting into Euler's Equation gives:

$$V - \frac{3F}{2} + F = 2 \dots\dots\dots 3.7$$

Simplifying further:

$$V = \frac{F}{2} + 2 \dots\dots\dots 3.8$$

Now to obtain a ratio that describes the average number of vertices per face we divide both sides by F:

$$\frac{V}{F} = 0.5 + \frac{2}{F} \dots\dots\dots 3.9$$

In large 3D Meshes, where the number of faces is significantly high the term $\frac{2}{F}$ becomes negligible since it becomes zero as the mesh grows in complexity. This leads to the ideal V/F ratio being approximately 0.5, this ratio represents the average number of vertices associated with each face in well-formed triangular mesh. The reciprocal value gives the F/V ratio, which indicates the average number of faces that share a single vertex. Therefore if:

$$\frac{V}{F} \approx 0.5 \dots\dots\dots 3.10$$

Then:

$$\frac{F}{V} \approx 2 \dots\dots\dots 3.11$$

These ratios are inversely related to each other, and together they define the geometric balance and efficiency of the mesh structure. A model with a V/F close to 0.5 and an F/V close to 2 suggest that the mesh is well formed and structurally efficient. Deviations from these values can indicate irregularities such as over-tessellation or under tessellation, non-manifold edges, or redundant vertices that may affect the performance and accuracy of the 3D reconstructed model.

In the context of project medusa, these ratios play a crucial role in evaluating the geometric quality and computational efficiency of the reconstructed 3D model. Since the objective of this research is to create and optimized and accurate real-time 3D scanning application, it is not enough to only compare file sizes and visual appearances, the internal mesh structure must also be mathematically sound.

By analysing the V/F and F/V ratios of each reconstructed object, it becomes possible to assess how efficiently the generated mesh uses its vertices to define the surface geometry. A model that maintains ratios close to the ideal values indicates that the application is producing high quality meshes that are both visually accurate and computationally lightweight, without unnecessary geometry that would increase the file size or processing time.

Eulers geometric theory provides a fundamental mathematical framework for

validating mesh topology. Therefore, by grounding the evaluation of project medusa's results in Euler's principles, this research establishes a quantitative and scientifically supported method for measuring the structural integrity and overall quality of the 3D reconstructed model.

Chapter 4: Implementaion

This chapter outlines the development process of the mobile application as part of this research work, In which an IOS mobile application is designed and developed to facilitate real-time 3D object reconstruction also validate the feasibility and efficiency of the proposed solution in the pervious chapter. This chapter is organised in the following way: Section 4.1 discusses the development environment and setup. Section 4.2 explains the system architecture of the application. Section 4.3 Lists the core implementation features of the system. Section 4.4 discuss the implementation challenges.

4.1 Development Environment and setup

Project Medusa is specifically designed to enable real-time 3D object reconstruction by combining both photogrammetry and LIDAR scanning techniques. The primary purpose of this application prototype is to validate the feasibility and efficiency of the solution defined in methodology chapter, and confirm the proof of concept for the objectives of this research by developing a fully functional system specifically built for LIDAR-enabled IOS devices.

Project Medusa prototype was primarily developed using swift programming language within Xcode IDE, both of which are technologies developed by Apple Inc. for creating software applications for Apple devices, including MacOS, IOS, Watch-OS, and TVOS. Project Medusa leveraged the capabilities of ARKit, Reality Kit and Scene Kit to enhance the efficiency of the application and follow the best practices that is recommended by Apple for app development on their respective platforms.

Moreover, the MVVM software architecture was adopted to guarantee a clear separation of concerns regarding the application's main logic, data handling, and user interface. Additionally, to manage the various states of our application FSM logic was employed to control the flow of capturing process ensuring a smooth transition between states from initialization of the capture to processing phase and eventually to completion of the scan.

Project Medusa mobile application enables users to simultaneously capture high-quality images along with depth data, thus resulting in an accurate and visually detailed 3D reconstructed model. The processing of these models happens in real-time, entirely on-device, thus eliminating the need for any external computing platform or software.

The application supports real-time preview and data manipulation, and it allows for universal export of those reconstructed 3D model to any device that supports it, through various mediums such as email services, wireless sharing, and instant messaging applications. The results of project medusa can be used in various virtual environments such as Unreal Engine and Blender, which can be utilized in media production and video game development.

4.1.1. Development Environment

Given the main objectives of the application is to make 3D scanning accessible on mobile smartphones, it was imperative to utilize a mobile smartphone device that is equipped with all the necessary sensors and components to test the application and demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed prototype. Therefore, a thorough search was conducted for a mobile device that integrated all the required components, leading to the selection of iPhone Pro models.

These devices feature a built-in LIDAR sensor and a 48-megapixel camera sensor, which allows for the capture of high-quality images crucial for this research work. These iPhone devices operate on IOS as their primary operating system, which is Apple's mobile phone operating system that is widely used and its very well known for its performance, ease of use and security features.

In order to natively develop an application for IOS devices, one is required to use swift programming language. This allows full access to device-level capabilities, including the complete control over the memory, GPU, and the individual sensors such as the LIDAR sensor and the camera utilities. Moreover, swift is a highly performant programming language thoroughly optimized to leverage the raw power of Apple devices. When combined these elements create a powerful mobile application that is capable of scanning models in real-time, and also

reduce the processing time it takes to reconstruct the scanned 3D model.

4.2 System Architecture Overview

The software architecture of Project Medusa prototype was designed with a strong emphasis on modularity and maintainability, to allow for the future expendability. Therefore, MVVM architecture, being a common choice for mobile application development due to its promotion of modularity, scalability, and enhanced maintainability was the perfect choice to implement Project Medusa based on the outline that it provides.

Combined with FSM computational model for state management, and transition between the various states of the application. Allowed for complete control over the flow of the application's phases. Thereby enhancing the 3D scanning process in Project Medusa.

4.2.1. Project Structure- MVVM Architecture

MVVM is one of the most widely used architectural patterns in the development of software applications, particularly for mobile devices. It offers a robust separation of concerns of the project main logic, thus improving the overall structure of the mobile application and enabling scalability for future development. MVVM architecture was implemented in the following way:

- **Model:** This layer is responsible for the management and storage of data that is obtained from the scanning process. This data includes the captured images and point cloud data acquired by the LIDAR sensor. Point cloud data is a collection of points in a 3D space, each of those points has coordinates (X, Y, Z) and also contains supplementary information such as intensity, colour and surface normal. These point clouds are later combined during the processing stage to generate the 3D model.
- **View Model:** This layer is responsible for the application logic, effectively serving as the connection between the model layer and the View layer. It processes various user actions during application usage, such as initiating as scan. It also triggers capture process, monitors the changes that are

occurring within the application, ensures that appropriate data is passed from the view to model layers, and manage's the FSM state transitions.

- **View:** this layer is responsible for presenting the applications user interface and displaying the various controls with which the user can interact with and operate the application properly. It dynamically reacts to changes that are occurring behind the scenes in the view model layer, presenting dynamic and reactive content such as scan states, 3D models previews and instructional guidance for the user. The utilization of swift UI framework simplifies this process due to its reactive nature of binding user interface components to the underlying logic of the mobile application.

This implementation of MVVM software architecture ensures that Project Medusa allow for future expandability and maintainability, while preserving the performance and flexibility of the current version of the software, Making the project more modular and easier to comprehend. Figure 4.1 below shows the MVVM architecture design of Project Medusa:

Figure 4.1 Project Medusa System Architecture

4.2.2. State Management - FSM Logic

To manage the various states of Project Medusa and control the flow of the application the FSM computational model was used. This model is highly effective in design systems with a limited, predictable and well-defined number of possible states and the transition between those states. It proves particularly useful for an application like project medusa, which relies on behaviour changes over time based on user input.

Another benefit in using FSM is its flexibility when it comes to designing systems that are time driven or event driven. FSM can handle both of those system types, and it can adapt to the systems functionality and requirements, however their implementation is slightly different depending on the system type. This allows Project Medusa to be more flexible, adaptable and achieve a smoother experience to the user. Figures 4.2 and 4.3 below depicts the diagram and the various states that available in Project Medusa:

Figure 4.2 FSM diagram for Project Medusa

```
enum ModelState {
    case notSet
    case ready
    case capturing
    case prepareToReconstruct
    case reconstructing
    case viewing
    case completed
    case restart
    case failed
}
```

Figure 4.3 The defined states in Project Medusa code

The states defined within Project Medusa are detailed as follows:

- Not Set: This represents the initial state of the application where no operation has commenced. By default, it selects the “Object Capture” mode. Its primary purpose is to prepare the application for initialization and allow the user to calibrate the application, making it ready for the scan.
- Ready: In this state, the user has decided to initiate the capture, and the scan is initialized with configured sensors, making it ready to begin the capture process. its main purpose is to guide the user in selecting the dimensions of the real-life object intended for capture.
- Capturing: this state is where the images and point cloud are captured by the camera and the LIDAR sensor respectively. The primary purpose of this phase is the acquisition of data from the sensors as the user manoeuvres around the object or scene.

- **Prepare to reconstruct:** This state indicates that the capturing process has been completed, and the application is ready for data processing. its main purpose is to handle the organization and cleanup of the data obtained from both sensors.
- **Reconstructing:** This is the state where the actual processing of the captured data occurs, generating a 3D model mesh based on the LIDAR data and applying textures derived from the concurrently captured images. its main purpose is to fuse both captured data sets and output a 3D model mesh based on the acquired information.
- **Viewing:** In this state, the generated 3D model is ready for user inspection. Users can interact with the model, including rotating, scaling, and comparing the generated result with the actual 3D object.
- **Completed:** This state signifies that the entire scanning and processing of the 3D model is complete, and the generated model is ready to be saved to the device and shared to a computer or another mobile phone. Upon reaching this state, the user has the option to either initiate a new scan or export the existing one if satisfied with the outcome.
- **Restart:** This state is triggered when the user indicates a desire to discard the current scan and commence a new one Upon activation, system memory is cleared, and the FSM resets to the “READY” state.
- **Failed:** This state occurs when an error is detected within the application (poor scan quality, inadequate lighting, or a sensor malfunction). When this state is reached, the user is informed of the error and provided with an option to retry the process.

The predefined states enable a streamlined implementation of application logic, clearly defining the application’s behaviour. This structured approach also simplifies management when switching between capture modes, such as from “object capture” to "Scene Capture,” as these states can be reused without the need for redefinition, thus enhancing the overall code debugging and

maintainability.

4.3 Core Implementation Features

The Project Medusa application has been meticulously designed and engineered to leverage the full capabilities of Apple's native frameworks and libraries. This is achieved specifically by utilizing the advanced hardware sensors of the iPhone Pro Model, such as its 48-megapixel camera array and sophisticated LIDAR sensor. By implementing a robust set of core useful features, the application aims to deliver superior results compared to its competitors.

These features are implemented in a manner that allows for the seamless integration of LIDAR depth data and photogrammetry texture data, which are obtained from high-quality captured images, thereby enabling real-time 3D object reconstruction directly on the device. The application is built upon MVVM and guided by the FSM computational model for state management, thus ensuring modularity, scalability, maintainability, and effective resource management.

4.3.1. Mode Selection

The user experience of the Project Medusa starts with a mode selection mechanism presented on the main camera feed in the form of a toggle button. This allows the user to choose between the (object capture mode) and (scene capture mode) based on their specific preference. This selection is crucial for adapting the hybrid capture process to either acquire individual real-life objects or a broader scene within the surrounding environment.

Upon launching the application, the user is greeted with the primary view of the live camera feed that is powered by ARKit's ARView instance within the Swift UI interface. This live camera feed serves as the shared canvas for real-time object capture and displays user guidance buttons and instructions. Figure 4.4 below illustrates the primary view of the application alongside other UI elements and visual cues:

Figure 4.4 Primary View of Project Medusa

The primary logic and state management of this process are controlled by the FSM. The selection of the capture mode triggers a transition in the application state from one mode of capture to the other. For instance, choosing “Object Capture Mode” triggers the FSM to initiate the (ObjectReadyForCapture) state whereas “Scene Capture Mode” transition to a (SceneReadyForCapture) state. This ensures that the application’s behaviour and subsequent processing are correctly configured for their respective capture modes, as demonstrated by the code snippet in Figure 4.6 below:

To facilitate the different capture modes, users are presented with a toggle button allowing them to change the mode of capture depending on their use case’s. upon selecting a capture mode, visual cues provide feedback to the user, informing them of the active capture mode. The figures below illustrate both scenarios in detail:

Figure 4.5 Scene Mode Vs Object Mode

The respective ARKit configuration adaptation for both capture modes dictate the AR session configuration. For instance, the “Object Capture Mode” configuration generally focuses on tracking individual, moderately small real-life objects or a confined designated area around the object. Upon initiation of this mode, the user encircles the object intended for scanning, which streamlines object-specific scanning and minimizes unwanted background data. Conversely the AR session configuration of the “Scene Capture Mode” is designed for capturing larger and unbounded object or environments enabling the user to freely navigate and map the environment.

```
switch appModel.captureMode {
  case .object:
    DispatchQueue.main.async {
      logger.log("Scene mode selected!")
      appModel.captureMode = .scene
    }
  case .scene:
    DispatchQueue.main.async {
      logger.log("Object mode selected!")
      appModel.captureMode = .object
    }
}
```

Figure 4.6 Model Selection Code Snippet

4.3.2. Object Bound Box

one of the most critical features of Project Medusa application is the object bounding box, which appears following the initiation of a scan. Its purpose is to define the overall volume of the target object before data capture. This is achieved by implementing an interactive 3D bounding box that appears within the live camera feed, implemented using ARKit and Reality Kit frameworks.

Once the capture process is initiated by the user, the application leverages ARKit's world tracking feature to understand the surrounding environment. The initial detection, scene calibration and volume estimation of the real-life object are performed by ARKit, and semi-transparent cube is rendered around the actual real-life object within the live camera feed. This cube features an outlined frame that distinguishes it from the object, making it easier for the user to perceive the real object and recognize its adjustable nature, as shown in the Figures 4.7 below:

Figure 4.7 Object bounding box

The adjustable nature of the bounding box allows the user to translate the bounding box cube along the X, Y and Z directions, which is implemented using Scene Kit. This enables the user to accurately center the cube around the object. Additionally, the bounding box can be scaled to encompass larger objects in real life, guaranteeing a more detailed and accurate scan.

Furthermore, bounding box rotation is available for objects with complex geometrical shapes, allowing the user to align the object with the main axes, potentially enhancing with the distinct volume of the real-life objects.

The adjustable 3D cube bounding box serves as a fundamental guide for the user to define the precise volume of the real-life object. All subsequent data captures from both the LIDAR sensor and camera are restricted to the volume defined by this bounding box. This significantly optimizes computational resources during data capture, on-device processing, and object reconstruction stages by excluding irrelevant data and reducing noise from the surrounding environment, focusing solely on the users intended target. This ultimately leads to a more efficient and higher-quality scan of the real-life object.

4.3.3. Orbit-Guided Capture System

To acquire comprehensive data, from the sensors and maximize the detail of the object capture within the application, an orbit-guided system has been implemented. This system addresses the issues of complete object coverage, particularly for objects with complex geometrical shapes by dividing the scanning process into segments of different orbital paths. The system utilizes ARKit's robust world tracking and real-time pose estimation feature to guide the user through each segment, thereby enhancing reconstruction quality, as illustrated by the code snippet in Figure 4.8 below:

```
func determineCurrentOnboardingState() -> OnboardingState? {
    guard let session = objectCaptureSession else { return nil }

    switch captureMode {
    case .object:
        let orbitCompleted = session.userCompletedScanPass
        var currentState = OnboardingState.tooFewImages
        if session.numberOfShotsTaken >= AppDataModel.minNumImages {
            switch orbit {
            case .orbit1:
                currentState = orbitCompleted ? .firstSegmentComplete : .firstSegmentNeedsWork
            case .orbit2:
                currentState = orbitCompleted ? .secondSegmentComplete : .secondSegmentNeedsWork
            case .orbit3:
                currentState = orbitCompleted ? .thirdSegmentComplete : .thirdSegmentNeedsWork
            }
        }
        return currentState
    case .scene:
        return .captureInAreaMode
    }
}
```

Figure 4.8 Mode Selection Code Snippet

The fundamental concept of the segmented capture system involves dividing the scanning process into predefined vertical segments or orbits: a medium orbit, a low orbit, and high orbit. This strategic segmentation ensures that both the camera and lidar sensor capture the object from various height angles, thereby decreasing occlusions and increasing surface coverage.

It is important to note that the orbits are not fixed paths but rather theoretical guidance zones relative to the predefined object bounding box (as outlined in section 4.3.2) the application dynamically calculates the object's height ranges for each orbit based on the object's initial estimated dimensions, which are defined by the bounding box relative to the object's height.

During each segment the user is guided through the scanning process with instructions and visual cues presented through the UI and rendered on top of the live camera feed. These UI elements inform the user of their vertical position, for instance, “move higher” or “move lower” depending on the user’s hand position during the scan. This assists the user in achieving the optimal scanning approach and desired results.

The application also offers real-time feedback by utilizing ARKit’s transform feature, which is employed to determine the user initial position, relative position, and orientation to the object. Visual indicators are displayed to the user to show the progress of the scan in real-time as they move 360 degrees around the object. This presented as a progress circle overlay, which functions as a progress bar or “fill bar” corresponding to the current segment’s completion. This updates dynamically as the user moves around the object, prompting the user to maintain an optimum distance and complete the full circular path for each segment, as shown in Figure 4.9 below:

Figure 4.9 Segment Completion Indicator

The transition between segments is handled by the FSM. A segment is considered complete when the application determines that sufficient image data and depth data have been captured from all angles within the object bounding box. This is achieved by the ARKit framework. Upon completion of an orbital

segment, the application guides the user to move to the next designated orbit- from medium to low to high orbit- each with its own segment and data capture, as shown in Figure 4.10 below:

Figure 4.10 Segment Transitions

4.3.4. Real-time Model Generation

One of the foundational features of Project Medusa's user experience (UX) and data quality assurance is the ability to visualize the 3D model generation in real-time directly within the live camera feed during the scanning process. This serves as a crucial feedback mechanism for the user allowing them to observe the point clouds and images captured during the scan. This feature is implemented using ARKit's world tracking feature along with Scene Kit and Reality Kit rendering frameworks provided by Apple, enabling the user to dynamically evaluate scan coverage and ensure the capture of every significant detail.

The main interface of Project Medusa is seamlessly integrated into the Live Camera Feed. Throughout the capturing process, this view continuously displays the mobile phone live camera feed, providing an augmented reality setting for the user to visualize the object or environment they intend to capture. Overlaid on the live camera feed, a dynamically generated 3D component is displayed, representing the model's progress and evolution, gradually blending with the real environment as the object reconstruction advances further, Figure 4.11 below shows the component in action:

Figure 4.11 Model Generation Component phases

As the user slowly moves around the object's environment, ARKit's mesh anchor

feature plays a crucial role in calibrating the initial position of the LIDAR sensor and providing a preliminary, rough mesh representation of the object in real-time. This mesh component, displayed on top of the camera feed, is continuously updated and refined as more data is captured from the LIDAR sensor.

It displays the raw point clouds transmitted from the LIDAR sensor. These points are typically rendered as small dot particles using scene Kit scene particle system and scene node geometry features, which are dynamically updated with each frame captured by both sensors this allows the user to instantly observe where the LIDAR data is being sent and the density of the point clouds during the scan.

Likewise, to help the user in understanding the overall object coverage, another component is added around the progressive 3D model that overlaps the camera feed. This component visually signifies the image taken from all angles. It materializes on the main display when the capturing process starts, depicted as a circle of vertical, unconnected lines. As the user moves around the object this circle updates as more data is obtained from the camera, progressively filling the gaps in the circle.

As part of the scanning process, during each segment of the capture, the user must move 360 degrees around the object. When a segment is completed, the circle resets, and the user must start anew, capturing the object from all angles to fill the gaps in the circle. Once all sides of the circle are completed and data is captured, this signifies that the segment is finished and notifies the FSM to transition to the next state.

4.3.5. Real-time Processing and Rendering Pipeline

The real-time characteristic of the progressive 3D model generation is achieved through an enhanced on-device pipeline. As new images and point cloud data are captured, they are sent to a lightweight iterative reconstruction process this process consciously updates a temporary scene node geometry model, displaying the current state of the 3D model.

This method of progressive mesh generation and texturing is computationally demanding and requires careful resources management. Techniques such as

multithreading for background tasks and mesh simplification have been employed for the real-time preview of the object. This ensures a smooth user experience at a reasonable frame rate, while simultaneously preserving high-resolution data for the final refinement and reconstruction.

This instant visual feedback system provided by the real-time model generation is vital for user guidance. Enables the user to identify gaps in the progressive 3D model, re-scan those identified gaps, adjust the scanning path and angle to ensure complete coverage of the entire object, and verify accuracy by observing the quality of the scan in real-time. This leads to a more accurate 3D scan of the object by allowing corrective actions to take place during the scanning phase itself, this instant visual component significantly enhances the overall scan quality and efficiency by transforming a traditionally blind capture process into an interactive and informative guidance system that improves the object scanning process.

4.3.6. Data Alignment and Reconstruction

Upon the successful completion of the multi-segment segment scanning process, the applications state transitions from data capture to the most crucial phase of the reconstruction process which is the data alignment and reconstruction of the 3D model based on the captured data, in the previous segments.

This process occurs entirely on device and is orchestrated to efficiently process the diverse datasets captured from the LIDAR sensor and the camera. The dense point clouds and high-quality images from the scanning process are processed into a unified, high quality 3D model this achieved by the FSM transitioning into the reconstruction state.

- Initial data preparation: the raw, unfiltered data acquired from the capturing stage includes LIDAR point clouds, which result from the depth data captured by the LIDAR sensor and provide accurate spatial measurements. The images taken from various angles. The images will undergo feature matching across overlapping images and will be bundled together to reconstruct camera poses and the 3D points of the model.

- **Data Alignment:** to accurately align these two distinct data sets, the iterative closest point ICP is employed. This process is handled by the Reality Kit Framework to iteratively minimize the distance between corresponding points in the LIDAR point cloud data and the photogrammetry data. This method precisely registers the image-derived geometry with the LIDAR-derived structure, ensuring the correction of any minor misalignments resulting from separate data acquisition by both methods and user movements.
- **Data Combination:** once both of data sets are aligned and organized, they are combined into a single unified dataset. This combined data generates a new point cloud that benefits from the geometric accuracy of the LIDAR and the high-quality texture detail and density provided by the photogrammetry technique.
- **Meshing:** as the application state transitions into reconstruction the combined data will be computed by the (PhotogrammetrySession) class, which is a core feature within Reality Kit framework. The (PhotogrammetrySession) takes the combined data and generates an opaque 3D mesh that outlines the actual geometric shape and structure of the real-life object. It then applies the high-quality images textures obtained from the original images onto the mesh structure, resulting in a highly detailed and geometrically accurate generated 3D model.

The approach, with its integrated pipelines that leverages the power of apples native technologies along with its devices, effectively transforms unorganized LIDAR data and Images in a high-fidelity, high-quality, reusable 3D asset, thereby confirming the efficiency of the 3D model scanning and reconstruction on mobile devices.

4.3.7. Multithreaded Processing

To maintain the application responsiveness, the entire process reconstruction process, including data alignment, data combination and mesh generation is handled by asynchronously in the background. To achieve this, the power of Grand Central Dispatch (GCD) is leveraged. GCD is a system-level API

developed by Apple that allow efficient handling of concurrent tasks on Apple's main operating systems, such as MacOS and IOS. This allows for the offloading of intensive tasks and computations from the Main UI thread to a dedicated background thread, ensuring that the applications UI remains smooth throughout the model reconstruction. Figure 4.12 shows some of the background tasks that are happening during reconstruction:

Figure 4.12 Background Tasks during Reconstruction

4.3.8. 3D Viewer and Interaction

Upon the successful reconstruction of the 3D model, the application state automatically transitions into the viewing state, loading the generated model onto the screen within a built-in environment. This integrated environment offers the user the ability to interact with the object in real-time and allows for side-by-side viewing of the generated model with the real-life object in an augmented reality view for visual comparison. This feature significantly enhances the user experience (UX) capabilities of the application and facilitates the confirmation of the reconstructed models.

The viewing functionality is implemented using (ARQuickLookController), a robust and powerful component within apple's quick look framework. This framework provides strong capabilities for displaying and interacting with the 3D models generated by the application, as well as viewing these objects in an AR experience. When the generated model is complete and the application state transitions into the viewing state, the quick look view presents a UI View with two separate modes for interaction:

- **Virtual Environment View:** in this view mode, the generated model is displayed within a virtual space, where users can freely rotate, scale, and pan the 3D object using interactive multi-touch gestures. This allows for a complete inspection of the object's geometry, texture, and overall fidelity of the generated model from all angles, as shown in Figure 4.13 below:

Figure 4.13 Virtual Environment of Project Medusa

- **Augmented Reality View (AR):** in this view mode, the generated object is displayed within the user's real-world surroundings. This enables the user to visually compare the generated object with the real-life object that was scanned in the previous phases, validating the generated model's accuracy against the physical object it represents. Within the AR view, users retain full control over the model's position, scale, and rotation. This real-time interaction is facilitated by ARKit's world tracking features, which strengthen the Quick Look framework, Figures 4.14 and 4.15 below show the AR view of the application:

Figure 4.14 Augmented Reality View #1

Figure 4.15 Augmented Reality View #2

The 3D interactive view implemented in Project Medusa significantly enhances the application's user experience by offering immediate visual validation of the accuracy of the reconstructed model. It allows users to manipulate the generated assets and confirm the quality of their scans and subsequently prepare their models for external integration with other platforms and 3D software applications. The utilization of quick look simplifies this process and eliminates the need for a complex custom 3D engine within the application while still maintaining fluid and responsive UI.

4.3.9. Object Masking

Project Medusa also includes an object masking feature, which is one of the features in Reality Kit framework that will play a significant role in optimizing the size of the generated 3D model. Object masking main functionality is to isolate the desired object that is currently being scanned from its background and surrounding environment, resulting in a cleaner more focused 3D model.

This removes the unnecessary background noise when the data is being scanned, thus optimizing the file size of the generated model compared to the other existing solutions. It's worth noting that object masking is only available when the user selects object capture mode when they initially want scan the object and it's not available in scene capture mode since we want to capture more area when it comes to capturing a scene. The code in the figure 4.16 below shows the implementation of object masking in project medusa:

```
private fun startReconstruction() throws {  
    var configuration = PhotogrammetrySession.Configuration()  
    if captureMode == .scene {  
        configuration.isObjectMaskingEnabled = false  
    }  
}
```

Figure 4.17 Object Masking Code Snippet

As shown in the figure 4.17 below, when masking is set to on it significantly improve the clarity and definition of the scanned object by eliminating extraneous data, whereas when masking is set to off retains some of the captured environment noise, which can detract from the quality of the 3D model reconstruction.

Figure 4.16 Masking on VS Mask off

This feature optimizes the models that are generated by Project Medusa in terms of size complexity while still maintaining the same quality and performance that Project Medusa Application has to offer.

4.3.10. Model Export and Sharing Functionality

Project Medusa Application is designed with comprehensive sharing and exporting capabilities, enabling users to seamlessly integrate the reconstructed 3D models into various of external workflows and share these assets across multiple platforms. This feature is essential for utilizing the reconstructed models in game development, virtual production, and other multimedia applications that support the use of 3D models. Below are some of the functionality and features that are available in Project Medusa:

- **On Device Storage and Organization:** the generated 3D models within the application are automatically saved to the application local storage, specifically within the document's directory, utilizing the File Manger API. These files are presented in a dedicated section of the application, referred to as the "library", which is designed to display previously saved scan projects. This library section of Project Medusa functions as a file browser, dynamically retrieving the file contents form the storage directory and displaying them as a card component with the object's images serving as the thumbnail. This

Figure 4.18 Library View of Project Medusa

enhances the UI, UX accessibility and asset management by allowing the users to preview scanned objects, view their previous scans and manage their digital assets directly within Project Medusa. Within the library, users can revisit previous scans, re-export, share or delete previously captured models, as shown in the 4.18 Figure below:

- **Universal Sharing Capabilities:** to ensure that Project Medusa has a wide range of interoperability with other platforms, the application leverages IOS's native sharing API, primarily (UIActivityViewContorller). This is a system-level component that allows users to export the generated model in .USDZ file format and share it across various channels which include:
 - **Direct Messaging:** the generated models can be sent directly via well-known instant messaging applications such as WhatsApp and Telegram, both of which natively support the .USDZ file format, allowing for preview and sharing across IOS devices.
 - **Email Services:** Users can attach the generated Model to their mail drafts and it to any desired email recipient.

- Airdrop: this is a file-sharing feature exclusive to devices within the Apple ecosystem. The generated model can be easily and wirelessly transferred to any IOS or MacOS machine, where it can later be used in other virtual environments such as Unreal Engine for further processing and game development purposes. This provides a seamless sharing experience between Apple devices and improves accessibility within the application. Figure 4.19 below shows the universal sharing functionality in Project Medusa:

Figure 4.19 Universal Sharing View of Project Medusa

- Files App Integration: The (UIActivityViewController) component also allows the user to save the generated 3D models directly into the device storage, outside of Project Medusa’s local storage sandbox. These models can later be viewed in IOS’s default Files Application, which enables them to be uploaded to cloud platforms such as iCloud, OneDrive, Google Drive, and Dropbox cloud Storage. This implementation enhances data persistence and accessibility across multiple platforms. The figure below shows the file app integration in Project Medusa

Figure 4.20 Files App integration

- USDZ File Format: Project Medusa exclusively supports model exports in the Universal Scene Description (USDZ) file format. This implementation is driven by several technical considerations:
 - Apple Ecosystem Optimization: Developed in Collaboration by Pixar Studios and Apple, the USDZ file format is meticulously optimized for apple devices. It provides native support for 3D content and unprecedented performance for AR applications, along

with seamless integration with apple's native frameworks, which played a crucial role in project medusa's design and development, allowing for the best possible on-device performance and graphic fidelity.

- Rich Feature Support: USDZ file format efficiently bundles mesh geometry, surface textures and materials into a single, small-sized package, making it ideal for sharing and mobile distribution. It also provides consistent rendering across multiple platforms.
- Growing Industry Adoption: USDZ has garnered significant interest in the realm of 3D model generation and development, particularly in real-time AR applications. It has found its way into various workflows due to its compatibility with desktop 3D software such as Blender, Autodesk Maya, Unity Game Engine and most importantly Unreal Game Engine.

while other file formats such as OBJ, FBX, STL exist in the real of 3D graphics, some of these file formats are not yet supported on Apple Platforms for On-device generation. However, applications like Polycam and 3D Scanner allow their object to be exported in these file formats by generating the model Via a backend service, which does not occur on-device thus making the model generation process substantially slower compared to project medusa.

Focusing solely on USDZ for Project Medusa not only simplifies the development process but also maximizes compatibility within the main Apple Ecosystem, without introducing the complexity of managing multiple file format-specific peculiarities or external format conversion libraries that might negatively impact application performance.

This robust export implementation ensures that the generated 3D models are not confined to the project medusa application but can be easily utilized and distributed within professional 3D software and other Multimedia workflows.

4.4 Implementation Challenges

Despite the successful design and development of Project Medusa, various design, practical and technical challenges presented themselves throughout the implementation stage. These challenges underline the limitations of the current state of mobile hardware and software technologies, and the natural complexity of implementing real-time 3D scanning. Each of these challenges and issues required detailed consideration and focus during the design, development, and testing phases. The challenges that occurred during development are addressed as follows:

4.4.1. Limited Hardware Compatibility

Project Medusa required the use of both a high-resolution camera and a LIDAR sensor. These hardware components are only available in iPhone Pro models, substantially limiting the range of devices that are capable of supporting Project Medusa. This compatibility limitation heavily reduced the accessibility and scalability of Project Medusa being available for more mobile devices.

Another issue was that most of the devices that support Google's Android OS lack the necessary sensors that were required for our experiment work. Most Android devices now days come with high-resolution camera modules however they lack a LIDAR sensor on their devices. This was a big issue since Project Medusa requires the use of the LIDAR sensor, for this purpose Project Medusa was only designed to be supported on Apple's iPhone Pro models. The figure 4.21 below shows the camera modules of Apple devices compared to Android devices:

Figure 4.21 iPhone Camera Module VS Android Devices

4.4.2. Cross-Platform Challenges

The limited hardware compatibility also led to another issue regarding the design and development of the application, Project Medusa was primarily developed for IOS ecosystem due to the necessary hardware requirements being present on iPhone Pro models. This introduced a major challenge for cross-platform development of Project Medusa, since the initial design draft and requirement of the application recommended the application to be available on multiple platforms such as Google’s Android devices and potentially Microsoft Windows devices.

Another factor that changed the initial design of the application was the lack of support for LIDAR application development on other platforms, since most of Android devices lack the required sensor there was a very limited amount of frameworks and libraires that were necessary not just develop the LIDAR scanning application but for the real-time processing as well, thus making cross-platform deployment very difficult to achieve.

Another factor was the native support of Apples frameworks and libraries that

were required such as ARKit, Reality Kit and Scene Kit being only available on Apple devices. developing Project Medusa for Android OS would have required complete re-implementation or custom developed solution of those native APIs. Furthermore, Androids Fragmented device ecosystem poses a lot of challenge accessing low-level hardware components since there are a lot of Android device manufactures with their own version of Android being used on their respective devices.

4.4.3. Device Overheating Challenges

Capturing 3D depth data and images from both the LIDAR sensor and Camera module, and processing them in real-time is a very computationally intensive task on a small mobile device. during extended scanning sessions the iPhone Device tends to overheat around the camera module which hinders the performance of Project Medusa. And the occasional use of the Flash component to illuminate the environment only added more fuel to the over-heating fire.

These issues presented a great challenge for the development of Project Medusa, for this purpose the optimization of the scanning process was required throughout the project, through FSM state management, multi-threading and efficient background task handling optimizations, Project Medusa managed limit the overheating for a longer period of time by turning of all of the sensors and data capture the minute the scanning process is finished. Though for a very prolonged use the device will still experience overheating around the camera module area of the device. The Figure 4.22 below shows the usage of the application during scan process and during model processing stage of Project Medusa:

4.4.4. Low Light Environments

Figure 4.22 Resource Usage of Project Medusa

Since photogrammetry heavily relies on the actual quality of the image taken by the user, and low-light environments generally impact the clarity and sharpness of the image negatively, it instantly became a challenge to consider in the design of Project Medusa, even though the LIDAR sensor helps in capturing the depth data of the real-life object, capturing the raw textures of the real object can be really challenging during scan in a low-light environment.

Although project medusa features the use of the “Flash” component to be set to on during scan to add some light to the environment, the combination of low light and visual noise can significantly reduce the overall accuracy and visual fidelity of the reconstructed model to a point where it doesn’t process the part of the real-life object that was in the low light environment, which is evident in Figure 4.23

below:

Figure 4.23 Light Environment vs Dark Environment

4.4.5. Reflective and Shiny surfaces

Reflective, shiny or polished surfaced objects such as mirror, glass or metal surfaces, introduce a challenge for both the camera sensor and the LIDAR sensor as well. In the case of the camera, the light reflections distort the image textures on the reconstructed model surface. In the case of the LIDAR sensor, it confuses the depth measurement of the object, and in combination it will lead to generating inaccurate point clouds or holes, disfiguring and damaging the surface of the reconstructed model. Figure 4.24 below shows the scanning result of reconstructed model of a shiny object:

Figure 4.24 Shiny object Reconstructed Model

4.4.6. Capturing Small Objects

Small-Scale objects with intricate details generally end in less accurate models being generated, it will still reconstruct the model similar to the real-life model however, there might be a lot of noise around the small parts of the reconstructed object, the resolution limits of mobile LIDAR sensors and the focal distance of the camera restrict the ability to capture sufficient data on very small-scale items. Figure 4.25 below shows a reconstructed model of a very small Formula 1 car:

Figure 4.25 Formula 1 Car Reconstructed Model

4.4.7. Capturing Object Under-Side

One of the most persistent challenges in the field of 3D object reconstruction is capturing the under-side of an object without rotating or repositioning the object to scan from below, for instance an object like a Rubik's cube (a cube shaped toy object with each of the sides having different colour) is really challenging to capture all the sides of it without rotating it to uncover the bottom side. This makes a large portion of the object remain incomplete and the object as whole under-detailed.

While the orbit-guided scanning is implemented in Project Medusa to improve the coverage of the reconstructed models, the bottom surface still poses a challenge during scan and generates inaccurate objects post-processing. Figure 4.26 below shows a reconstructed model of a Rubik's cube missing its under-side:

Figure 4.26 Rubik's cube Reconstructed object missing its under side

4.4.8. Software Restrictions by Apple:

Apple's software ecosystem, while robust, puts heavy limitations on low-level access to certain hardware components that are available on their devices. Some of the internal functionalities of the LIDAR and photogrammetry frameworks are undocumented in their developer documentations and are inaccessible by design. The challenges that Project Medusa faced in this front are as follows:

- No access to raw depth maps or point cloud manipulation.
- No public API's for customizing the photogrammetry Session beyond the presets that were set by Apple.
- Restriction to USDZ exports only

Restricting deeper optimization and advanced feature integration. Moreover, the dependence on USDZ format and the absence of native support for other 3D file formats adds complexity to third-party integration. This is due to Apple's security features which make their devices more reliable in terms of security in the cost of limiting accessibility to their low-level hardware components.

Custom detail level			
	Triangles	Memory size	Supported platforms
Reduced	▲	■	iOS, macOS
Medium	▲ ▲	■ ■	
Full	▲ ▲ ▲	■ ■ ■ ■	
Raw	▲ ▲ ▲ ▲	■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■	macOS
Custom	▲ ▲ ▲ ▲	■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■	

Figure 4.27 level of detail restrictions by Apple

Chapter 5 Results and Discussion

This chapter contains the test results of our experiments of the proposed solution against the other solutions in the market, and the discussion regarding these results. Section 5.1 discusses the performance evaluation of the proposed prototype. Section 5.2 discusses the file size evaluation of the project. Section 5.3 explains the quality assessments of the prototype compared to the other solutions. Section 5.4 compares the visual results of the prototype compared to the other solutions. Section 5.5 presents the prototype results in action with integration with 3rd party software. Section 5.6 discuss the findings of the research work.

5.1 Performance Evaluation

This section of the research meticulously details the performance evaluation of project medusa in relation to the other competing benchmarked 3D scanning applications. The primary metric for assessing the performance was the processing time that was required to generate the 3D models from the captured data in each respective application.

For this purpose, a set of eight distinct real-world objects were scanned using Project Medusa, Reality Scan, Polycam, and 3D Scanner App. With all tests conducted under consistent environmental and hardware conditions to ensure fair and reliable evaluation of the results. The processing time for each object across all applications were meticulously recorded and are presented Table 5.1 as processing time in minutes:

Table 5.1 Processing Time Comparison in Minutes

Processing time in Minutes				
Object	Project Medusa	Reality Scan	Polycam	3D Scanner App
Ship	01:13	02:03	03:27	11:06
Doll	01:22	03:09	02:10	08:28
Perfume	00:44	01:55	02:04	06:45
Xbox Controller	01:01	01:22	02:13	12:55
Eiffel Tower	00:58	04:23	02:41	04:47
Laptop	02:11	08:14	03:45	08:01
Camera	01:10	06:40	02:49	06:31
Lego Car	01:03	01:47	02:25	04:11
Average	01:13	03:42	02:42	07:50

As it's shown in Tables 5.1 Project Medusa consistently exhibited the shortest processing time across all of the tests when compared to the other solutions. The average processing time was approximately 1 minute and 13 seconds which is substantially lower than the average times recorded for Reality Scan (3 minutes and 41 seconds), Polycam (2 minutes and 41 seconds), and 3D Scanner App had the slowest processing time with the average of around (7 minutes and 50 seconds). Figure 5.1 below shows the average processing time between each application:

Figure 5.1 Average Processing Time of each Application

Specifically, Project Medusa processed objects such as “Perfume” in just 44 seconds and the “Eiffel Tower” in 58 Seconds, showcasing its exceptional efficiency for smaller to medium-sized objects. Even objects which are more complex such as the “Laptop” Project Medusa recorded time of 131 seconds which is significantly faster than Reality Scan at 494 seconds, 3D scanner App at 481 seconds and Polycam while generally faster than Scan and 3D Scanner App, still exhibited longer processing times compared to Project Medusa, with an average of 161 Seconds. The figure below shows the processing time for each

object in every application:

Figure 5.2 Processing time of each object by each App

The remarkable reduction in processing time achieved by Project Medusa can be attributed to its optimized design by leveraging the raw performance of the mobile device to process the data, and handle the integration of on-device LIDAR data for rapid spatial structuring with photogrammetry for detailed texturing. Project Medusa’s architecture, along with the use of apple’s native libraries and frameworks specifically on-device processing pipeline, and the hardware capabilities of LIDAR-Enabled Devices along with efficient multithreaded processing facilitated by the GCD contributed heavily to reducing the processing time, by separating the main UI thread, from computationally intensive tasks, ensuring smooth user experience while accelerating the reconstruction process. This performance superiority directly addresses the research objective of enhancing the processing speed in real-time 3D scanning solutions on mobile devices.

5.2 File Size Evaluation

This section presents a comparative analysis of the file size of the 3D models generated by project Medusa and the other benchmarked applications. File size is a critical indicator of application efficiency, impacting storage requirements, ease of sharing and loading times in various 3D environments. The file size for

each reconstructed object were measured across all four applications and are summarized, along with their averages, in Table 5.2.

Table 5.2 File size comparison

file size in mb				
Object	Project Medusa	Reality Scan	Polycam	3D Scanner App
Ship	12	227.3	7.91	61
Doll	7.4	137.5	2.79	150
Perfume	5.6	57.9	5.16	141
Xbox Controller	6.7	76.6	5.37	134
Eiffel Tower	8.2	126.8	3.22	150
Laptop	9.3	224.2	6.35	152
Camera	7.2	271.3	5.8	145
Lego Car	8.1	86.1	5.61	142
Average	8.0625	150.9625	5.27625	134.375

As indicated in table 5.2 Polycam consistently generated the smallest average file size at approximately 5.28MB. Project Medusa followed closely with an average file size 8.06MB consistently coming second in every test. In contrast Reality Scan and 3D Scanner App produced significantly larger file sizes, averaging approximately 150.96MB and 134.38MB, respectively, the chart below shows the average file size of each application:

Figure 5.3 Average File Size of Each Application

The data indicates that project medusa, while not the absolute smallest in terms of file size maintains a highly optimized file size footprint, which is vital for mobile devices storage and efficient transfer. The relative compact file sizes of the models that are generated by Project Medusa and Polycam are particularly advantageous for real-time applications and environments where bandwidth and storage are critical considerations, such as game development and virtual production. The chart below shows the file size of each object generated by each application:

Figure 5.4 File Size of Each Object by Each Application

The substantial difference in file sizes between Project Medusa, Polycam and Reality Scan along with 3D Scanner App can be attributed to several factors related to their underlying reconstruction methodologies and default output settings. Applications like Reality Scan and 3D Scanner App often generate meshes with significantly higher polygon count (as will be discussed in section 5.3), which directly contribute to larger file sizes. While higher polygon counts can sometimes imply greater geometric detail, they also incur higher computational and storage overhead. Project medusa’s ability to produce comparatively small file sizes, while still aiming for high-quality reconstruction, underscores its efficiency in data processing and mesh optimization.

This efficiency is partly achieved through its on-device processing pipeline and sensible use of the USDZ file format, which is optimized for mobile distribution and efficient bundling of mesh geometry, textures, and material into a compressed 3D package. This strategic choice in selecting the right technologies and careful designing of the application architecture along with object masking feature (as discussed in chapter 4.3.9) contributes to the overall file size optimization. This outcome aligns with the research objective of optimizing the results of the application, particularly in terms of resource efficiency and usability for various digital workflows and virtual environments.

5.3 Quality Assessment

This section presents a detailed assessment of the quality of the 3D models generated by Project Medusa against the other solutions, focusing on mesh density as represented by vertex count and polygon count or (faces), and also the mathematical quantities of V/F and F/V ratios, these metrics are crucial for quantifying the geometric fidelity, structural efficiency, and overall level of detail of the reconstructed 3D models by each of the applications. Table 5.4 and Table 5.5 shows the Vertex count and the polygon count of each individual object respectively, Tables 5.6 and 5.7 show the V/F and F/V Ratios of each object in each application respectively, and the average data for these quality indicators across all eight scanned objects for each application are presented in Table 5.8:

Table 5.3 Vertex Count Comparison

Vertices				
Object	Project Medusa	Reality Scan	Polycam	3D Scanner App
Ship	12476	1708571	31560	30723
Doll	11584	1326368	19951	28864
Perfume	3282	439483	28480	28844
Xbox Controller	7659	702527	29606	28773
Eiffel Tower	7478	1207369	14296	29539
Laptop	12482	2828369	29749	29823
Camera	11403	4552452	28881	28706
Lego Car	8944	769850	29179	29364
Average	9414	1691874	26463	29330

Table 5.4 Polygon Count Comparison

Faces (polygon count)				
Object	Project Medusa	Reality Scan	Polycam	3D Scanner App
Ship	25000	3417818	50000	49999
Doll	23172	2652728	33869	49999
Perfume	6560	878938	49999	49999
Xbox Controller	15305	1405018	49999	50000
Eiffel Tower	14952	2414746	23993	49999
Laptop	25000	5656638	49999	50000
Camera	22802	7648277	49999	50000
Lego Car	17892	1539696	50000	50000
Average	18835	3201732	44732	50000

Table 5.5 V/F Ratio Comparison

V/F				
Object	Project Medusa	Reality Scan	Polycam	3D Scanner App
Ship	0.49904	0.499901106	0.6312	0.614472289
Doll	0.499913689	0.500001508	0.589063746	0.577291546
Perfume	0.500304878	0.500015928	0.569611392	0.576891538
Xbox Controller	0.500424698	0.500012811	0.592131843	0.57546
Eiffel Tower	0.500133761	0.499998344	0.595840453	0.590791816
Laptop	0.49928	0.500008839	0.5949919	0.59646
Camera	0.500087712	0.595225827	0.577631553	0.57412
Lego Car	0.499888218	0.500001299	0.58358	0.58728
Average	0.4998841195	0.5118957078	0.5917563608	0.5865958986

Table 5.6 F/V Ratio Comparison

F/V				
Object	Project Medusa	Reality Scan	Polycam	3D Scanner App
Ship	2.003847387	2.000395652	1.584283904	1.627412688
Doll	2.000345304	1.999993968	1.697609142	1.732226996
Perfume	1.998781231	1.999936289	1.755582865	1.733428096
Xbox Controller	1.99830265	1.999948756	1.688813078	1.737740243
Eiffel Tower	1.999465098	2.000006626	1.678301623	1.692643624
Laptop	2.002884153	1.999964644	1.680695149	1.676558361
Camera	1.999649215	1.680034627	1.731207368	1.74179614
Lego Car	2.000447227	1.999994804	1.713561123	1.702765291
Average	2.0004652832	1.9600344209	1.6912567816	1.7055714297

Table 5.7 Average Quality metrics

Application	Vertices(vertex count)	Polygon count (faces)	V/F	F/V
Project Medusa	9413.5	18835.375	0.499884119	2.000465283
Reality Scan	1691873.625	3201732.375	0.511895708	1.960034421
Polycam	26462.75	44732.25	0.591756361	1.691256782
3D Scanner App	29329.5	49999.5	0.586595899	1.70557143

As observed in Table 5.7 significant variations exist in the mesh density among the applications. Reality Scan generated Models with the Highest average vertex count of (1,691, 873.625) and polygon count of (3,201,732.375) following Reality Scan, 3D scanner app and Polycam produced models with substantially lower, yet comparable, average vertex count of (29,329.5 and 26,462.75, respectively)

and polygon counts of (49,999.5 and 44,732.25, respectively). In contrast Project Medusa consistently generated models with the lowest average vertex count (9,413.5) and polygon count of (18,835.375).

The V/F (vertex-to-face) ratio provides insight into the average number of vertices per face, where a lower ratio (approaching 0.5 for purely triangular meshes) suggest efficient tessellation in the model. Project Medusa exhibited a V/F ratio of approximately (0.49988) which is remarkably close to the ideal theoretical value of 0.5 for triangular meshes, indicating highly efficient and well-formed mesh geometry. Reality Scan Also showed a low V/F ratio of approximately (0.51189), indicating its models despite their high density, also maintain a relatively efficient vertex-to-face relationship. Polycam and 3D Scanner App, however presented higher V/F ratios of approximately 0.59175 and 0.58659, respectively. These higher ratios suggest that, for a given number of faces these applications might be utilizing slightly more vertices, potentially indicating less optimal mesh density or the presence of more complex face structures if not strictly triangulated.

Conversely, the F/V (face-to-vertex ratio reflects the average number of faces sharing each vertex, with a higher ratio generally indicating a more compact and interconnected mesh. Project medusa achieved an F/V of approximately (2.00046) which is extremely close to the theoretical ideal value of 2.0 for well-formed triangular meshes where each interior vertex is shared by multiple faces. Reality Scan also demonstrated a Strong F/V ratio of approximately (1.96003). both Polycam and 3D Scanner App recorded a lower F/V ratios of approximately (1.69125 and 1.70557, respectively.) these lower F/V ratios suggest that, on average, vertices in models generated by Polycam and 3D Scanner App are shared by fewer faces compared to Project Medusa and reality Scan, which could imply a less compact mesh structure or a higher proportion of boundary edges if the meshes are not fully diverse.

This divergent result in mesh density reflects different optimization strategies

Figure 5.5 3D Scanning Applications Performance/ Quality Spider Chart

employed by each application. While Reality Scan Prioritizes Capturing an extremely high level of detail, leading to massive polygon counts and larger file sizes (as discussed in section 5.2), project medusa demonstrates a strategic balance. Despite generating models with significantly fewer polygons and vertices, Project Medusa V/F and F/V Ratios indicate that it's meshes are topologically complete and efficiently constructed.

This indicates that Project Medusa Achieves high level of quality by optimizing the geometric structure rather than merely maximizing polygon count. This optimization is crucial for on-device processing and for generating models that are readily usable in performance-sensitive applications like game engines without extensive post processing for mesh simplification.

The efficiency of Project Medusa in generating geometrically complete Models with lower polygon counts is a direct consequence of its data combination and alignment during the reconstruction stage of the application. By leveraging the

precises spatial data from the LIDAR sensor to define the fundamental geometry, and then integrating for texture application, the prototype avoids the generation of extraneous polygons that might otherwise result from purely photogrammetric methods attempting to infer depth from 2D images alone. This approach ensures that the reconstructed models maintain geometric accuracy and visual fidelity while remaining resource efficient, aligning with the research objectives of optimizing the results and improving the visual quality of 3D object reconstruction within practical constraints.

5.4 Visual Comparison

This section provides a qualitative assessment of the visual elements and geometric quality of the reconstructed models that are generated by Project Medusa in comparison with the other software applications. While quantitative metrics such as Processing time, file size, polygon count, vertex count, V/F and F/V ratios (as discussed in the previous section 5.3) provide incredible insight into mesh density and mesh efficiency, visual inspection is vital for evaluating aspects such as texture resolution, surface smoothness, and overall fidelity to the real-world object.

This evaluation was conducted by taking individual images of every object that is generated by each of the applications in comparison. To ensure unbiased observation of their aesthetic and structural characteristics. Each object's reconstruction from Project Medusa, Reality Scan, Polycam, and 3D Scanner App was scrutinized for details such as clarity of the textures, presences of noise, smoothness of surfaces and how well they preserved their original appearance of the real-life object.

5.4.1. Visual Comparison of “Camera” Model

The reconstructed 3D models of the” Camera” model (Figure 5.41) from Project Medusa, Reality Scan, Polycam, and 3D Scanner App are presented one by one for visual comparison. The raw image below shows the model image in real life under luminous conditions and below the real image is the result of each scanning application.

Figure 5.6 Real Image of the Camera

Figure 5.7 Project Medusa Generated Result of the Camera

Project Medusa's rendition of the "Camera" object exhibits a strong resemblance to the real-life object, demonstrating excellent geometrical structure and texture quality, making the reconstructed object visually accurate, with no noise or artifacts whatsoever. This proves that the combined photogrammetry and LIDAR scanning approach of project medusa has a lot of potential to make its way to mainstream media and be used commercially.

Figure 5.8 Reality Scan Generated Result of the Camera

Reality Scan reconstructed model of the “Camera” Object demonstrates good geometrical structure of the object, however the texture of the object appears to be distorted on the surface of the object and a lot of artifacts and noise are generated around the object especially on the bottom of the object due to object masking not being available. Thus making the object visually inaccurate compared to Project Medusa’s result despite having more polygon counts and vertices to work with.

Figure 5.10 Polycam Generated Result of the Camera

Polycam’s result of the “Camera” object shows a very good geometrical structure and texture application almost resembling the real-life object, however there are a lot of noise and artifacts that are generated from the bottom of the Camera object, mainly because masking of the object is not available on Polycam and the shadows of the Camera object can be seen in the picture which is not ideal for use in other applications.

Figure 5.9 3D Scanner App Generated Result of the Camera

3D Scanner app’s reconstructed “Camera” Object similar to Polycam’s rendition shows good geometrical structure and texture application, however a lot of noise

and random artifacts are generated surrounding the object, and the shadow of the camera appears to be visible on the bottom surface of the object, thus rendering the object visually inaccurate.

Figure 5.11 Visual Comparison of Camera Object Unreal Engine

In summary, for the “Camera” object comparison in (Figure 5.11) all the applications showed amazing geometrical structure and texture application, especially Project Medusa shows the most geometrically accurate and excellent texturing on the models surface making the reconstructed model appear to a complete replica of the real-world object, Reality Scan despite having the most polygon and vertex count among the applications it showed the most inaccuracies compared to the others, Polycam and 3D Scanner App showed similar results, they were geometrically accurate and the texturing were very good however a lot of noise and artifacts were generated in the final model.

5.5 Integration with 3rd- Party Software

The final results of Project Medusa were used in other 3rd party software to evaluate the usability and flexibility of the reconstructed 3D models, which heavily depended on their compatibility with 3rd party software that are mainly used for multimedia purposes. Project Medusa was developed with this in mind, by allowing the user to export the 3D reconstructed models they have scanned to

any software that they are familiar with.

The exported models in Project Medusa can be shared universally to any other platform that supports USDZ file format, and it can be shared by different channels such as instant messaging applications, email services, and wireless sharing. The USDZ file format is widely compatible with many well know software applications and tools that are used by many professionals for multimedia purposes, some of those tools are including but not limited to:

- Unreal Game Engine
- Blender
- MeshLab
- Apple keynote

This section will demonstrate the use-cases of the reconstructed models of Project Medusa in 3Rd party applications and how they could transform the realm of 3D multimedia to a more immersive 3D space. It worth mentioning that only the result of Project Medusa are explained in this section and the results of the other solutions are not mentioned in this section since it out of scope of this research.

5.5.1. Unreal Game Engine

Used extensively throughout this study to validate the visual quality and photorealism of the generated models of project medusa in game development environment. Models exported from project Medusa retained both geometry and texture quality, integrating seamlessly with Unreal Engine 5 real-time rendering pipeline. The figure 5.12 below shows all the reconstructed models of Project Medusa in Unreal Engine:

Figure 5.12 all reconstructed models of Project Medusa in Unreal Engine

The real-time environment of unreal engine allowed for very rapid testing and evaluation. The main use-case of these reconstructed models is to be put in a virtual game environment to tell a story in the game and this object most of the time need to create a realistic shadow around the surrounding environment. Unreal Engine supports Real-time Lighting and allows the developer to control the light inside of the environment where they develop their game. The constructed model of Project Medusa inside Unreal Engine can create those shadows and it will update based on the lighting conditions of the light in real-time. The Figure 5.13 below shows the Real-time Light control of Unreal Engine with the reconstructed “Camera” Object of project Medusa:

Figure 5.13 Real-time Light control of Unreal Engine

5.5.2. Blender

Blender is a widely used, open-source modelling and animation software that is used by many professional to create, model, animate and render 3D models. and it's heavily utilized in the field of game development. Blender supports USDZ file format, and it can easily be imported and manipulated by the user. Once imported the model maintained its mesh topology, scale and texture application. Figure 5.14 shows Project Medusa Camera Object in Blender:

Figure 5.14 Project Medusa Camera Object in Blender

One key observation was that the level of mesh cleanliness for project medusa reduced the need for heavy retopology or manual cleanup. The model could instantly be placed anywhere in the scene and used for any multimedia purposes.

5.5.3. MeshLab

MeshLab was utilized to evaluate the technical integrity of the 3D meshes generated by Project Medusa. As a robust open-source 3D model processing tool, MeshLab provided very detailed insights about the mesh information such as the polygon count, vertex count and distribution and surface geometry. Figure 5.15 shows Project Medusa camera object in MeshLab:

Figure 5.15 Project Medusa Camera object in MeshLab

Project Medusa Models were found to be very geometrically accurate and structurally sound, with very precise geometry in most cases. MeshLab also facilitated the visual comparison of Project Medusa scans against ideal mesh topologies, reinforcing the application's overall potential. It is worth noting that MeshLab by default did not support USDZ file format, and the models had to be converted to OBJ format; this was done by writing a Python script to convert every .USDZ into OBJ file format. The script can be seen in Appendix 2.

5.5.4. Apple Keynote

Apple Keynote offers native support for USDZ models, making it a suitable tool

for educational and presentation purposes. Project Medusa reconstructed models can easily be embedded into the slides, they could be manipulated in real-time during a presentation-rotated, zoomed, and examined from all angles. Figure 5.16 shows Project Medusa Camera object in Apple keynote:

Figure 5.16 Project Medusa Camera object Apple Keynote

this opens up use cases in academic environments, museums, and product design showcases, where physical objects can be digitized and shared with interactive, high-fidelity visualizations. Project Medusa seamless integration with Apple ecosystem ensures that users can present 3D content without additional conversion or technical setup.

5.6 Findings

Project Medusa was the experimental part of this research, where we designed and developed the application from scratch using Apple's latest technologies and hardware devices, and the experimental evaluation of Project Medusa has produced several key findings into the feasibility and performance of combined photogrammetry and LIDAR scanning solution on mobile devices. Some of those findings are:

1. Performance Efficiency: Project Medusa has consistently shown faster processing time compared to the other solutions that were compared against it. This is accredited to the use of the native Apple frameworks and libraries, along with design decision of processing the model completely on-device, showcasing the raw power of today's mobile devices and hardware capabilities. Thus, eliminating the latency that is linked with cloud or server-side computation.
2. File Size Optimization: Project Medusa's reconstructed models consistently generated smaller file sizes without sacrificing any geometrical detail or texture quality, thus underlining the effectiveness of its real-time rendering pipeline and mesh simplification strategies.
3. Model quality: Project Medusa exhibited superior texture fidelity and geometrical accuracy, despite having the least polygon count and vertex count compared to the other solutions the model consistently showed near-ideal results in the quality assessments. This is accredited to the data alignment process of combining the photogrammetry and LIDAR data using ICP produced geometrically reliable, texture rich and visually rich reconstructed 3D models.
4. User Experience and Guidance: Features such as orbit-guided capture, real-time model feedback, and FSM-based state transitions drastically enhanced users control over the capture meanwhile minimizing scanning errors, by implementing an easy to operate and friendly UI and guiding the user through the scanning process. Thus, improving the result of the reconstructed models.
5. Compatibility and integration: models produced by Project Medusa were successfully imported into industry-standard tools like Unreal Engine, MeshLab and Blender. Showcasing the readiness of the reconstructed models which can instantly be used in various creative workflows and in any multimedia project.

These findings confirm the feasibility and viability of Project Medusa as a next-

generation mobile 3D scanning solution, capable producing visually accurate models with less time, that can later be seamlessly integrated into any virtual environment the user desires.

5.7 Summary

This chapter highlighted the performance capabilities; model quality and comparative results of Project Medusa compared to the existing widely known solutions. The comprehensive evaluation that was conducted involved the measurements of Processing time, file size, vertex and polygon count, and mesh quality of each model in each application. The result of the evaluation confirmed that the proposed prototype outperformed competition in both efficiency and visual fidelity, while also offering real-time feedback, intuitive user guidance, and compatibility with major 3rd party platforms.

Chapter 6 Conclusions and Future work

This thesis investigated the feasibility and the effectiveness of using a combined photogrammetry and LIDAR scanning approach for real-time 3D object reconstruction on mobile devices. The developed application, Project Medusa, Leverages Apple's iPhone LIDAR sensor, advanced camera hardware, and native development frameworks to deliver high-quality, accurate 3D models suitable for game development and other multimedia use cases.

The primary objectives of this research were archived as follows:

- Objective 1: Project Medusa is a hybrid Photogrammetry and LIDAR scanning mobile application developed as experimental work of this research and its capable of capturing data in real-time and process it completely on-device. Results of which can later be used in various virtual environments for different multimedia purposes.
- Objective 2: Project Medusa had a superior Processing time and was consistently faster than any other application it was tested against beating all of the other solutions by an average of 73 seconds.

Through iterative design and agile development methodology, a robust system architecture based on MVVM and state management using FSM contributed heavily to the performance of Project Medusa leading to significant improvement in processing time, model quality, and user experience.

6.1 Limitation

Despite the successful implementation of Project Medusa faced some serious challenges that were difficult to overcome, some of those limitations were:

- Project Medusa is only available on LIDAR-Enabled devices and it's not available on a device that does not support it.
- Surface textures and materials such as reflective surfaces, shiny, or complex

surface are hard to capture and scan.

- Low light environments pose an issue for the final scan processing and some area's might be missing from final result.
- Limited control over Apple's proprietary frameworks and data processing methods.
- Limited availability across multiple platforms such as Android and Windows.
- Since Project Medusa uses almost all of the components on the Camera Module at the same time, some overheating can be experienced during a prolonged usage of the application.

6.2 Future work

For future enhancements in this field, one can Focas on improving the following areas:

- Making the application compatible with other platforms, to support a wide range technologies and devices.
- Integrating AI-based noise filtering and AI based mesh cleaning.
- Adding support for other file formats like OBJ and FBX to further improve the integration with other software applications.
- Enabling collaborative scanning or Multi-device Capture and synchronization for large-scale environments.

6.3 Summary

This thesis has demonstrated that real-time 3D reconstruction using mobile hardware is not only feasible but also practical for real-world applications. by blending modern software architecture with native IOS capabilities, Project Medusa offers a compelling solution that pushes the boundaries of on-device 3D

Scanning. The proposed combined “hybrid” approach opens new roads for research and innovation in AR/VR, game development, education and beyond.

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Appendix 1

GitHub Repository of Project Medusa Application:

https://github.com/ZheerBarzan/project_medusa

Logo of Project Medusa Application:

Results of Project Medusa Application compared with other applications:

1) ship model

Real Model of a Ship object

Project Medusa result of Ship Object

Reality Scan result of Ship Object

Polycam result of Ship Object

3D Scanner App result of Ship Object

2) Doll Model

Real model of Doll Object

3) Eiffel Tower Model

Real model of the Eiffel Tower Object

4) Lego Car Model

Real model of the Lego car

Project Medusa result of Lego Car

Reality Scan result of Lego Car

Polycam result of Lego Car

3D Scanner App result of Lego Car

5) Xbox Controller Model

Real model of the Xbox controller

6) Laptop Model

Real Laptop Used For Scanning

Appendix 2

Python Script to convert every USDZ into OBJ file Format.

```
import os
import argparse
from pxr import Usd, UsdGeom
import trimesh
import numpy as np

def convert_usdz_to_obj(input_filepath, output_dir):

    print(f"Processing '{input_filepath}'...")

    # Extract base name without extension
    base_name = os.path.splitext(os.path.basename(input_filepath))[0]
    output_obj_filepath = os.path.join(output_dir, f"{base_name}.obj")

    try:
        stage = Usd.Stage.Open(input_filepath)
        if not stage:
            print(f" Error: Could not open USD stage from
'{input_filepath}'. Skipping.")
            return False

        all_meshes = []

        # Traverse the USD stage to find all UsdGeomMesh primitives
        for prim in stage.TraverseAll():
            if prim.IsA(UsdGeom.Mesh):
                mesh_prim = UsdGeom.Mesh(prim)

                points = mesh_prim.GetPointsAttr().Get()
                face_vertex_counts =
mesh_prim.GetFaceVertexCountsAttr().Get()
                face_vertex_indices =
mesh_prim.GetFaceVertexIndicesAttr().Get()

                if points is None or face_vertex_counts is None or
face_vertex_indices is None:
                    print(f" Warning: Skipping mesh '{prim.GetPath()}'
due to missing geometry data.")
                    continue

                vertices_np = np.array(points, dtype=np.float32)

                trimesh_faces = []
                current_index = 0
                for count in face_vertex_counts:
                    polygon_indices = face_vertex_indices[current_index :
current_index + count]
                    # Simple fan triangulation for polygons with more
than 3 vertices
                    if count >= 3:
                        for i in range(1, count - 1):
                            trimesh_faces.append([polygon_indices[0],
polygon_indices[i], polygon_indices[i+1]])
                    current_index += count
```

```

        if len(trimesh_faces) == 0:
            print(f"    Warning: No triangulated faces found for
mesh '{prim.GetPath()}'. Skipping.")
            continue

        # Create a trimesh object
        mesh = trimesh.Trimesh(vertices=vertices_np,
faces=np.array(trimesh_faces, dtype=np.int32))
        all_meshes.append(mesh)

    if not all_meshes:
        print(f"    No mesh geometry found in '{input_filepath}' to
convert to OBJ. Skipping.")
        return False

    # Combine all tri-meshes into a single scene and then export as
one OBJ
    # This handles USD files that contain multiple root meshes
    if len(all_meshes) > 1:
        combined_scene = trimesh.Scene(all_meshes)
        # dump(concatenate=True) will merge all meshes into a single
Trimesh object
        combined_mesh = combined_scene.dump(concatenate=True)
    else:
        combined_mesh = all_meshes[0]

    # Export to OBJ
    combined_mesh.export(output_obj_filepath)
    print(f"    Successfully converted
'{os.path.basename(input_filepath)}' to
'{os.path.basename(output_obj_filepath)}'.")
    return True

except Exception as e:
    print(f"    Error converting '{input_filepath}' to OBJ: {e}")
    return False

def main():
    parser = argparse.ArgumentParser(description='Convert USDZ files from
an input directory to OBJ files in a new output directory.')
    parser.add_argument('input_directory', help='Path to the directory
containing USDZ files.')
    parser.add_argument('--output_directory', '-o',
default='converted_objs',
                        help='Name of the new directory to store OBJ
files. Default is "converted_objs". '
                        'This directory will be created if it does
not exist.')

    args = parser.parse_args()

    # Ensure input directory exists
    if not os.path.isdir(args.input_directory):
        print(f"Error: Input directory '{args.input_directory}' does not
exist.")
        return

    # Create the output directory if it doesn't exist
    os.makedirs(args.output_directory, exist_ok=True)
    print(f"Output files will be saved to:
'{os.path.abspath(args.output_directory)}'")

```

```

converted_count = 0
skipped_count = 0

# Iterate through files in the input directory
for filename in os.listdir(args.input_directory):
    if filename.lower().endswith('.usdz'):
        input_filepath = os.path.join(args.input_directory, filename)
        if convert_usdz_to_obj(input_filepath,
args.output_directory):
            converted_count += 1
        else:
            skipped_count += 1
    else:
        print(f"Skipping non-USDZ file: '{filename}'")

print("\n--- Conversion Summary ---")
print(f"Converted: {converted_count} file(s)")
print(f"Skipped: {skipped_count} file(s)")
print(f"Output directory:
'{os.path.abspath(args.output_directory)}'")

if __name__ == '__main__':
    main()

```

خلاصة

لقد قيل إن الصورة تساوي ألف كلمة، لكنها قد تحتوي أيضاً على آلاف القياسات. يعرض هذا البحث "مشروع مدوسا"، وهو تطبيق هجين للمسح ثلاثي الأبعاد على الأجهزة المحمولة يُبسط ويُحسّن إعادة بناء الكائنات ثلاثية الأبعاد في الوقت الحقيقي من خلال دمج تقنيات الفوتوغرامميتري والمسح باستخدام الليدار، والتي يمكن استخدامها لاحقاً في البيئات الافتراضية مثل محرك Unreal. استلهم اسم المشروع من أسطورة مدوسا اليونانية التي كان بإمكان نظرتها أن تحوّل أي كائن حي إلى حجر، مما يعكس كيف يمكن للتكنولوجيا الحديثة أن تعيد بناء الأجسام الواقعية رقمياً بدقة ووضوح. الطرق التقليدية لإنشاء النماذج ثلاثية الأبعاد غالباً ما تكون مستهلكة للوقت، وتتطلب موارد كثيرة ومكلفة، خاصة لأغراض مثل تطوير الألعاب والرسوم المتحركة. لمواجهة ذلك، تم تطوير مشروع مدوسا كحل ميسور التكلفة، ودقيق، وسهل الاستخدام على الأجهزة المحمولة. يستخدم التطبيق منهجية Agile لتطويره واختباره بشكل تكراري، مما يضمن أن يكون متيناً، وذو أداء عالي، وسهل الاستخدام. يستفيد التطبيق من الأطر الأصلية لأبل مثل ARKit وRealityKit لمعالجة البيانات بالكامل على الجهاز نفسه، مما يلغي الحاجة إلى منصات حوسبة خارجية. شملت اختبارات التحقق والاعتماد مسح كائنات متنوعة ضمن ظروف محكمة، ومقارنة النتائج مع حلول موجودة أخرى مثل RealityScan وPolycam و3D Scanner App. أظهر مشروع مدوسا باستمرار أفضل أداء وجودة مقارنةً بالتطبيقات الأخرى. كما أنتج التطبيق نماذج ذات هندسة شبكية فعالة، كما يتضح من النسب القريبة للمثالية بين الرؤوس والأسطح (Vertex-to-Face) والعكس (Face-to-Vertex)، مما يدل على توازن بين الجودة والكفاءة الحسابية. يمكن تصدير النماذج النهائية بتنسيق USDZ ودمجها بسهولة واستخدامها في بيئات افتراضية احترافية مثل برامج التصميم ثلاثي الأبعاد، تحرير الفيديو، برامج الرسوم المتحركة، برامج العروض التقديمية، ومحركات الألعاب بما في ذلك Unreal Engine.

پوخته

دهوتریت وینه‌یهک به‌های هزار و شاهی همیه ، به‌لام دهکرتیت هزار پیاونه‌شی هه‌بیت .نهم توژی‌ینه‌ویه به‌نامه‌ی موبایلی سکانکردنی تیکه‌لأوی “پروژه‌ی میدوسا” دمخاته روو که بنیات‌نانه‌وی شته سی ره‌ه‌ندییه‌کان له کاتی راسته‌قینه‌دا ناسانتر و کارا تر دهکاته‌وه به تیکه‌ل‌کردنی زانستی فوتوگرامتری و ته‌کنیکه‌کانی سکانکردنی LIDAR ، که نه‌نجامه‌کانی دواتر ده‌توانریت له ژینگیه‌کی کومپيوته‌ر دروستکراوی وهک Unreal Engine به‌کار بهینریت. ناوی پروژه‌که له نه‌فسانه‌ی یونانی میدوسا نیلهام وهرگیراوه که به نیگا‌کانی دهیتوانی هه‌موو بوونه‌وه‌ریکی زیندوو بکاته نامرازیکي به‌رد، له هه‌مان کاتدا ته‌کنه‌لوژیای مؤدیرن ده‌توانیت به شیوه‌یه‌کی دیجیتالی شته‌کانی جیهانی راسته‌قینه به وردی و وردبینی بنیات بنیته‌وه .شیوازه ته‌قلیدیه‌کانی دروستکردنی مؤدیلی سی ره‌ه‌ندی زورجار کات به‌فیرؤده‌ر و سه‌رچاوه‌ی زوری ده‌ویت و تیچووی زوری ده‌ویت بو مه‌به‌ستی وهک په‌ر مپیدانی یاریه‌کان و نه‌نیمه‌یشن .بو به‌ر منگار بوونه‌وی نهم پروژه‌یه میدوسا وهک چار سه‌ریکی موبایل که تیچووی کهم و ورد و به‌کار هینس دؤسته په‌ری پندرا. به‌نامه‌که میتودولوژیای چالاکي به‌کار ده‌هینیت بو په‌ر مپیدان و تاقیکردنه‌وه دوبره‌بووه‌کانی، دلنایای ده‌دات له‌وی که به‌هیز و کارایی و به‌کار هینس دؤسته .ته‌کنه‌لوژیای ره‌سعی کومپانیای Apple وهک ARKit ، و Reality Kit به‌کار ده‌هینیت بو پرؤسیس‌کردنی داتا‌کان به ته‌واوی له‌سه‌ر نامیره‌که، نه‌مه‌ش پنیوستی به پلاتفورمی کومپيوته‌ری ده‌رکی نامینیت .تاقیکردنه‌وه و چه‌سپاندن پیکهاتبو و له سکانکردنی شته جیاوازه‌کان له ژیر بارودوخی کؤنترؤل‌کراودا و به‌راوردکردنی نه‌نجامه‌کان له‌گه‌ل چاره‌سه‌ر مه‌کانی تری هه‌بوو وهکو Polycam ، Reality Scanner App 3D Scanner App پروژه‌ی میدوسا به به‌رده‌وامی باشتترین کارایی و کوالیتی به به‌راورد به به‌نامه‌کانی تر پیشان دا. هه‌روه‌ها به‌نامه‌که مؤدیلی به نه‌ندازه‌یی توری کارامه به‌رهم هینا، وهک له ریژه‌ی نزیک له نایدیالی لوتکه بو رووخسار و رووبه‌رووی لوتکه‌دا نامازه‌ی پیکراوه، که هاوسه‌نگی له نیوان کوالیتی و کارایی نیشان ده‌دات .مؤدیله کؤتاییه‌کان، که به شیوه‌ی USDZ هه‌نارده ده‌کرتین ده‌توانریت به ناسانی په‌کبخرین و له ژینگیه‌کی کومپيوته‌ر دروستکراوی پیشه‌یی وهک نه‌مه‌کالای سی ره‌ه‌ندی، ده‌ستکاری‌کردنی فیدویو، نه‌مه‌کالای نه‌نیمه‌یشن، نه‌مه‌کالای پیشکه‌شکردن و بزونه‌ری یاریه‌کان به‌کار بهینریت، له‌وانه‌ش Unreal Engine .